

Climate adaptation and entrepreneurship in Kenya

Working Paper

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Abstract

While entrepreneurs provide critical climate adaptation services, their valuable on-the-ground perspectives and underlying motivations to tackle climate issues have been minimally studied, particularly in low- and middle-income country contexts. This working paper addresses this research gap by studying the values and motivations of diverse climate adaptation entrepreneurs in Kenya to identify key opportunities, challenges, and business models in this space. A mixed-methods approach is taken including literature review, quantitative survey, qualitative interview, thematic analysis, descriptive statistical analysis, and comparative analysis with community data. 22 entrepreneurs in the Nairobi Metropolitan area were purposively sampled. We find that entrepreneurs are primarily motivated by gaps or issues they perceive in the market or in the availability of adaptation services; knowledge of existing solutions to fill those gaps; a desire to bring affordable and locally appropriate solutions; and their inner ideals and desires for a climate-friendly future. The core values that motivate these entrepreneurs include innovation, preservation of the natural environment, access to services, and caring for others. Our respondents identified key opportunities to build synergies across value chains such that each player is not simultaneously serving as importer, maintainer, salesperson, and so on of these novel climate technologies. They also saw promise in circular economy approaches within the sector (e.g., in the creation of biofuels from waste). They cited that the most pressing challenges they face in running their businesses were lack of access to appropriate and patient finance, lack of technical capacity in novel innovative sectors, and lack of awareness amongst both consumers and regulators, leading to friction. They described that a consumer-led approach with a subscription-based payment structure was critical.

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1 Introduction

This study investigates the values that underpin and motivations that drive diverse entrepreneurs that work on local climate adaptation in Kenya to identify key opportunities, challenges, and business models to create inclusive climate adaptation impact.

Entrepreneurs are critical in facilitating economically sustainable climate adaptation, as recognized by the UNFCCC¹. Climate adaptation has brought about an increase in the pace of innovation and entrepreneurship, for instance in the energy², agricultural³, and water-sanitation⁴ fields. However, research has been largely focused on public sector adaptation and thus the entrepreneurial approaches involved in the development of innovations to address climate change remain poorly understood⁵. Furthermore, data on the range of business models and resultant innovations developed by entrepreneurs in the climate adaptation space is still in the nascent stage⁶, which limits our understanding of best practices in climate adaptation. This is particularly true in LMICs, which also suffer from so-called “adaptation deficits”⁷ (i.e., a lack of capacity to adapt due to institutional, financial, or technological capacities) and ergo require urgent attention.

Entrepreneurs are often erroneously treated as a homogenous group, obscuring their diverse motivations, worldviews, values, business strategies, and challenges. Despite this, it is known that female entrepreneurs in sub-Saharan Africa are known to engage in entrepreneurship for different reasons than men, and to face different vulnerabilities and challenges to their businesses including in the face of climate change⁸. Additionally, in agriculture, adaptation measures have been posited in various contexts⁹ to be influenced by the perception, contextual backgrounds, and demographic factors of farmers¹⁰.

In a similar way, entrepreneurs from different backgrounds and demographics may provide different climate adaptation solutions and run their businesses in different ways. Indeed, they may meet different adaptation needs based on varying types of climate vulnerability, which are

¹ UNFCCC. 2018. TEC Brief #12: Energizing Entrepreneurs to Tackle Climate Change. Bonn: UNFCCC secretariat. https://unfccc.int/ttclear/misc/_StaticFiles/gnwoerk_static/brief12/bd80d2dd55e64d8ebdbc07752108c52c/af75fb524aa042e2a4f795ba6f29196f.pdf

² Houda, K., & Triki, A. (2014). Entrepreneurship in the renewable energy sector. 2014 1st International Conference on Green Energy, ICGE 2014, 72–76. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICGE.2014.6835400>

³ Kangogo, D., Dentoni, D., & Bijman, J. (2020). Determinants of farm resilience to climate change: The role of farmer entrepreneurship and value chain collaborations. *Sustainability*, 12(3), 868.

⁴ Schaub-Jones, D. (2011). Market-based approaches in water and sanitation: the role of entrepreneurship. *Waterlines*, 5-20.

⁵ Niek ten Brinke, Joanne Vinke-de Kruijf, Leentje Volker & Nora Prins (2022) Mainstreaming climate adaptation into urban development projects in the Netherlands: private sector drivers and municipal policy instruments, *Climate Policy*, 22:9-10, 1155-1168, DOI: 10.1080/14693062.2022.2111293

⁶ Trapp, C. T., & Kanbach, D. K. (2021). Green entrepreneurship and business models: Deriving green technology business model archetypes. *Journal of cleaner production*, 297, 126694.

⁷ Fankhauser, S., & McDermott, T. (2014). Understanding the adaptation deficit: Why are poor countries more vulnerable to climate events than rich countries? *Global Environmental Change*, 27, 9–18.

⁸ Gannon, Kate Elizabeth, et al. "The triple differential vulnerability of female entrepreneurs to climate risk in sub-Saharan Africa: Gendered barriers and enablers to private sector adaptation." *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change* 13.5 (2022): e793.

⁹ Al-Amin, A. A., Akhter, T., Islam, A. H. M. S., Jahan, H., Hossain, M. J., Prodhan, M. M. H., ... & Kirby, M. (2019). An intra-household analysis of farmers' perceptions of and adaptation to climate change impacts: empirical evidence from drought prone zones of Bangladesh. *Climatic Change*, 156, 545-565.

¹⁰ Waibel, H., Pahlisch, T. H., & Völker, M. (2018). *Farmers' perceptions of and adaptations to climate change in Southeast Asia: the case study from Thailand and Vietnam* (pp. 137-160). Springer International Publishing.

known to vary based on social, economic, historic, and political factors¹¹. By capturing value-driven motivations, opportunities, and challenges of climate entrepreneurship in a demographically disaggregated way, pathways for inclusive environmental entrepreneurship to serve diverse climate adaptation needs can be mapped.

This study therefore aims to map the values and motivations of diverse climate adaptation entrepreneurs in Kenya to identify key opportunities and challenges that they perceive in this space as well as the best business models to create inclusive climate adaptation impact. Specifically, we aim to answer the following questions:

- What motivates entrepreneurs to engage in climate adaptation space?
- What are the most important impacts, opportunities, approaches, and challenges of entrepreneurship to support climate adaptation?
- How do the climate adaptation needs addressed by entrepreneurs correlate with or diverge from the adaptation needs of community members?
- What business models can help scale the innovation of local climate adaptation solutions?

Each of these questions is explored with an eye to diversity across entrepreneurs and their approaches, and with an eye to policy and financial implications. Specifically, we seek to clarify how policy and support programmes should be shaped to encourage climate adaptation entrepreneurship, to align entrepreneurial aspirations with community needs, and to scale inclusive impact.

The remainder of this working paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents the methodology undertaken in the study, including interview protocols and survey data analysis. Section 3 then presents the results. Section 4 offers a discussion and interpretation of the results with an eye to structural implications in policy and investment. Finally, Section 5 concludes.

2 Methodology

This study uses a mixed-methods approach to investigate the values and motivations of entrepreneurs that are developing innovations to address the challenges of climate change in Kenya. Their business models and perceptions concerning opportunities and challenges in the climate adaptation space are also examined.

2.1 Literature Review

A literature review was undertaken to understand. To validate the gaps identified by the authors, a systematic search of the literature was first undertaken using the Scopus search engine and the query string "climate adapt*" AND "entrepreneur*" AND "Kenya*" on 8th January 2024. The metadata, abstracts¹², and keywords of these results were exported for review. The abstracts,

¹¹ Thomas, K., Hardy, R. D., Lazrus, H., Mendez, M., Orlove, B., Rivera-Collazo, I., ... & Winthrop, R. (2019). Explaining differential vulnerability to climate change: A social science review. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 10(2), e565.

¹² Where abstracts were missing in the export, titles were searched in Google Scholar to locate the abstract. If the texts could not be found, or did not contain an abstract, the abstract section was left blank.

titles, and keywords were checked for: (a) direct study of Kenya¹³; (b) direct study of climate change or adaptation; and (c) direct study of entrepreneurship or business activity¹⁴. The references from these papers were also snowball-sampled at the authors' discretion and domain knowledge in the climate adaptation and entrepreneurship scholarship.

With the landscape of existing literature systematically studied, additional contextually-relevant literature was added to the review. Relevant Kenyan policy and grey literature were reviewed, as well as papers on the methodological lenses specific to this study. These were identified based on the authors' collective experience in this context.

2.2 Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with climate adaptation entrepreneurs across energy, agribusiness, and water-sanitation sectors in Kenya. A purposive sampling approach was undertaken, facilitated in partnership with the Kenya Climate Innovation Center (KCIC), and a database of startups in Africa produced within the Climate Compatible Growth programme. The full interview tool is available in Appendix A. It focuses on the following four dimensions:

- About the business: Motivation, intended impact (including in climate adaptation), customer base (including disadvantaged groups), changes over time.
- Business model: Ownership structure, prices, growth strategy, collaborators, risks, funding, inputs and supply chain.
- Climate adaptation: Previous customer adaptation practices, time-scale of impact.
- Entrepreneur perceptions: Opportunities, challenges, and business models for climate adaptation.

The interviews were audio-recorded with the consent of the participants, and later transcribed and translated. The collected interview data were thematically analysed to map business strategies, opportunities, and motivations across entrepreneurs. This analysis was done in accordance with the six-stage framework, (1) familiarisation with data; (2) generation of initial codes; (3) searching for themes; (4) reviewing themes; (5) defining themes; and (6) analysis and writing up as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006)¹⁵. We used Atlas.ti qualitative analysis software for descriptive and thematic analysis of textual data. The software was used to assess the frequency of code usage, explore co-occurrences of various codes, and facilitate the review and analysis of the data. A qualitative code book was generated using both inductive and deductive methods to serve as the basis for interpretative analysis of these data.

¹³ Where the geographic scope could not be determined from the abstract, title, and keywords, the paper text was examined.

¹⁴ Note that farming, agriculture, and fishing, when discussed in the context of income generation, are interpreted as a form of entrepreneurship or business. Tourism activities are also interpreted as business. Innovation may also be interpreted as entrepreneurship based on context.

¹⁵ Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.

Specific questions intended to elicit entrepreneur values were coded using the user-perceived value (UPV) framework¹⁶ as a basis. This framework indirectly identifies the true value of development initiatives by linking needs and wants to core values, facilitating value-informed decision-making. The individual value codes included (e.g., faith, aspiration, knowledge attainment, etc) fall within the following categories: Emotional Value; Epistemic Value; Functional Value; Indigenous Value; Intrinsic Value; and Social Significance Value. As the UPV codes are not specified to the study of entrepreneurs, not all included values were relevant. Therefore, as interviews were coded, the values which emerged most commonly were noted, and any values which appeared to be missing were added. The remainder of the interview text was coded inductively. The final code list is included in Appendix B.

2.3 Survey

A survey was also disseminated to the same entrepreneurs to elicit quantitative data about their businesses. Questions covered quantitative business information such as key products and prices, employment impacts, and finance strategies, as well as entrepreneur demographics. The surveys were analysed using descriptive statistics. The full survey tool is included in Appendix C.

2.4 Comparative Analysis with Community Data

The results from entrepreneur interviews and surveys were then compared with community survey data to understand alignment or divergence on climate adaptation priorities. The community dataset comprises 1,023 household surveys conducted in 2023 by the Climate Compatible Growth programme using the UPV approach. This survey elicited demographics, development priorities, and climate change fears and adaptation strategies. Here, the following survey questions are the focus for analysis:

- How worried are you about climate change?
- In your own words, how would you describe climate change?
- Describe what has changed in your community in recent years relating to climate change.
- What extreme climate event are you most worried about? Why are you most worried about this climate event?
- Given the chosen climate event - which 3 items are most useful to you?
- Which other environmental hazards affect you and your community?
- How do you mainly receive information about climate change?
- Have you received training or guidance which relates to climate change e.g., from the municipality, NGOs, community leaders or other bodies?
- What was taught in the training?
- Which skills would you like to develop further as a result of climate change and why?

¹⁶ Hirmer, S., & Guthrie, P. (2016). Identifying the needs of communities in rural Uganda: A method for determining the 'User-Perceived Value' of rural electrification initiatives. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 66, 476-486.

This analysis was compared with interview results to understand how community needs align or diverge from entrepreneur motivations and perceptions.

2.4 Ethics

To ensure the study's integrity, a risk and ethics assessment following the Medical Sciences Interdivisional Research Ethics Committee at the University of Oxford in accordance with the procedures laid down by the university for ethical approval for all research involving human participants was completed and approved with reference: R74082/RE001. It is covered by licence NACOSTI/P/23/21652. An assessment by the Strathmore University Institutional Scientific and Ethical Review Committee was also completed and ethical approval was given with reference: SU-ISERC1931/23. To protect the participants' identity, all data were anonymised. Quotes from participants are used in the discussion of the results; these are presented with representative pseudonyms.

3 Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study. First, the literature review is detailed. Then, interview and survey results are discussed, and compared with community needs data.

3.1 Literature Review

3.1.1 Systematic Search

A systematic search was undertaken as a starting point for analysis. The result of the systematic literature search is illustrated in Figure 1. The Scopus search elicited 257 results. Of these papers, 18 directly examined Kenya, and ten of these directly studied both climate change/adaptation and entrepreneurship/business.

Figure 1: Scopus search results as they align with the relevance criteria defined in section 2. Note that *n* refers to the number of papers and priority levels correspond with criteria met, where priority 1 means that all criteria are met and priority 2 means that two of the three defined criteria are met.

Instead of focusing on how businesses can contribute to broader climate adaptation, much of the literature identified in this search discussed primarily how businesses themselves can adapt to climate change¹⁷. This is of course important in the face of increasing risks (e.g., flooding from stronger El Ninos¹⁸) which are increasingly perceived as a “real threat” to business¹⁹. Within this literature, Berkhout (2011) uses three categories to categorise organisational adaptation: utility-maximising, behavioural, and institutional²⁰. Crick et al (2018), in their evaluation of how small and medium enterprises in Kenya and Senegal adapt to climate change²¹, instead differentiate between sustainable and unsustainable adaptation measures. Atela, Gannon, and Crick (2019) continue work in this tradition by deepening the analysis within female-led small businesses in Kenya, finding that female entrepreneurs are likely to turn to unsustainable forms of coping²². Shibia (2023) also discusses adaptive behaviours of small

¹⁷ Agrawala, S., Carraro, M., Kingsmill, N., Lanzi, E., Mulla, M., & Prudent-Richard, G. (2011). Private sector engagement in adaptation to climate change: approaches to managing climate risks OECD Environment Working Papers No. 39. OECD Publishing.

¹⁸ Gannon, K. E., Conway, D., Pardoe, J., Ndiyoi, M., Batisani, N., Odada, E., ... & Siderius, C. (2018). Business experience of floods and drought-related water and electricity supply disruption in three cities in <https://doi.org/10.1017/sus.2018.14>

¹⁹ Blundel, R., Baldock, R., Dadd, D., Schaefer, A., & Williams, S. (2014). Resilience and recovery: SME experiences of extreme weather events and other external threats. In: Institute for Small Business and Entrepreneurship (ISBE) 2014, 5-6 November 2014, Manchester.

²⁰ Berkhout, F. (2012). Adaptation to climate change by organizations. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 3(1), 91–106.

²¹ Crick, F., Eskander, S. M., Fankhauser, S., & Diop, M. (2018). How do African SMEs respond to climate risks? Evidence from Kenya and Senegal. *World Development*, 108, 157-168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.03.015>

²² Atela, J., Gannon, K. E., & Crick, F. (2018). Climate change adaptation among female-led micro, small and medium enterprises in semi-arid areas: a case study from Kenya. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93336-8_97

businesses²³ and households²⁴ in Kenya, with a focus on their use of formal and informal finance in the case of droughts and floods. The most common business sector discussed in these papers on the adaptation of businesses themselves was agriculture. This included discussion of climate-smart agriculture, for instance by Faling (2020) within the context of Kenyan policy²⁵ (e.g., including climate-smart agricultural practices). Some also discussed the vulnerability of farmers in the face of climate change. For instance, Carranza and Niles (2020) investigated their risk of food insecurity using data from Kenya, Uganda, and Senegal, and how this varies across genders²⁶. In sum, while these insights about adaptation within businesses is interesting, it is not the focus of this study, which instead aims to investigate how businesses support adaptation.

The only paper identified which focuses on entrepreneurial motivations identified by the authors studies a high-income context (i.e., the UK)²⁷. While Pauw and Pegel do provide some insight on private sector engagement on climate adaptation in developing countries, their work either takes a top-down approach without bottom-up entrepreneurial perspectives (i.e., analysing National Adaptation Programmes of Action²⁸) or foregrounds sector structure and responsibilities over motivations (i.e., in Zambia²⁹). As such, we could find no papers centering entrepreneur motivations to tackle climate change in LMICs in this search. This validates the literature gap we have identified and are working to fill.

3.1.2 Entrepreneur motivations to address climate change

There are few papers detailing entrepreneurs' motivations to tackle climate adaptation issues. One core piece of literature comes from Kaesehage, who highlights that entrepreneurs who address climate change have motivations specific to their business activity and level of maturity³⁰. These motivations are linked to distinct conceptualizations of time and place. Adding to this understanding, Block emphasises the importance of various conditions for entrepreneurial success in climate change adaptation, including prior career experience, altruistic motivations, financial motives, social networks, financial capital availability, and policies and regulations³¹.

²³ Shibia, A. G. (2024). Firms' use of formal and informal finance in coping with droughts and floods: experiences from Kenya. *Climate and Development*, 16(1), 9-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2023.2176187>

²⁴ Shibia, A. G. (2023). Households' coping mechanisms with droughts and floods using finance, non-finance and the social safety net measures: evidence from Kenya. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-023-03515-3>

²⁵ Faling, M. (2020). Framing agriculture and climate in Kenyan policies: a longitudinal perspective. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 106, 228-239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.01.014>

²⁶ Carranza, M., & Niles, M. T. (2019). Smallholder farmers spend credit primarily on food: gender differences and food security implications in a changing climate. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 3, 56. [\[https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2019.00056\]](https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2019.00056)(<https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2019.00056>)

²⁷ Kaesehage, K., Leyshon, M., Ferns, G., & Leyshon, C. (2019). Seriously personal: The reasons that motivate entrepreneurs to address climate change. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 157, 1091-1109.

²⁸ Pauw, P., & Pegels, A. (2013). Private sector engagement in climate change adaptation in least developed countries: An exploration. *Climate and Development*, 5(4), 257-267.

²⁹ Pauw, W. P. (2015). Not a panacea: Private-sector engagement in adaptation and adaptation finance in developing countries. *Climate Policy*, 15(5), 583-603.

³⁰ Kaesehage, K., Leyshon, M., Ferns, G., & Leyshon, C. (2019). Seriously personal: The reasons that motivate entrepreneurs to address climate change. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 157, 1091-1109.

³¹ de Block, D., Feindt, P. H., & van Slobbe, E. (2019). Shaping conditions for entrepreneurship in climate change adaptation. *Ecology and Society*, 24(1).

Kaesehage also proposed a continuum to help categorise climate entrepreneurship motivations³². The continuum categorises three motivations as a function of sense of time and sense of space.

The first category is the **climate opportunists**. Climate opportunists are individuals or groups who take advantage of climate change adaptation projects for their own interests, often to the detriment of the intended objectives. They can include public intellectuals who shape political discourse on climate change, such as ecological activists, smart growth reformers, and eco-modernists³³. Celebrity climate contrarians, who resist dominant scientific interpretations and advocate for special interests, are also considered climate opportunists³⁴. Furthermore, political populists, who blame elites for non-responsiveness to citizens' needs, can influence public support for climate mitigation policies³⁵.

The second category is the **integrative entrepreneurs**. Integrative entrepreneurs in climate change are individuals who drive change by using their agency to influence policy decisions at the local and regional levels³⁶. They play a crucial role in the policy formulation phase, ensuring that new climate policies are implemented³⁷. These entrepreneurs are particularly effective in problem framing and catalysing large-scale behavioural change related to climate change³⁸. In the urban context, they work within novel multisector networks, collaborating with nontraditional actors to bring about sustainability transitions³⁹.

The third category is **traditional entrepreneurs**. Traditional entrepreneurs in climate change, such as those in nature-based tourism, are influenced by their values and attitudes, which can impact their decision-making and adaptation strategies⁴⁰. However, these entrepreneurs may also be sceptical about the existence and impact of climate change, leading to a lack of adaptation strategies⁴¹. Policy entrepreneurs, on the other hand, play a vital role in addressing climate change by promoting significant policy change and catalysing large-scale behavioural change⁴². At the local and regional levels, governance entrepreneurs are key actors in climate governance, but there is a need for more research on their activities, strategies, and effects⁴³.

³² Kaesehage, K., Leyshon, M., Ferns, G., & Leyshon, C. (2019). Seriously personal: The reasons that motivate entrepreneurs to address climate change. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 157, 1091-1109.

³³ Nisbet, M. C. (2014). Disruptive ideas: Public intellectuals and their arguments for action on climate change. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 5(6), 809-823.

³⁴ Boykoff, M. T. (2013). Public Enemy No. 1?: Understanding Media Representations of Outlier Views on Climate Change. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 57(6), 796-817. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764213476846>

³⁵ Huber, R. A. (2020). The role of populist attitudes in explaining climate change skepticism and support for environmental protection. *Environmental Politics*, 29(6), 959-982.

³⁶ Jordan, A., Huitema, D., Schoenefeld, J., van Asselt, H., & Forster, J. (2018). Governing climate change polycentrically. *Governing climate change: polycentricity in action*, 3-26.

³⁷ Reimer, I., & Saerbeck, B. (2017). Policy entrepreneurs in national climate change policy processes. *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*, 35(8), 1456-1470.

³⁸ Mintrom, M., & Luetjens, J. (2017). Policy entrepreneurs and problem framing: The case of climate change. *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*, 35(8), 1362-1377. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399654417708440>

³⁹ Schroeder, H., Burch, S., & Rayner, S. (2013). Novel multisector networks and entrepreneurship in urban climate governance. *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 31(5), 761-768.

⁴⁰ Tervo-Kankare, K. (2023). Tourism and climate change adaptation in protected areas. In *Handbook on Tourism and Conservation* (pp. 73-85). Edward Elgar Publishing.

⁴¹ Saarinen, J., & Tervo, K. (2006). Perceptions and adaptation strategies of the tourism industry to climate change: the case of Finnish nature-based tourism entrepreneurs. *International Journal of Innovation and Sustainable Development*, 1(3), 214-228.

⁴² Mintrom, M., & Luetjens, J. (2017). Policy entrepreneurs and problem framing: The case of climate change. *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*, 35(8), 1362-1377.

⁴³ Huitema, D., Boasson, E. L., & Beunen, R. (2018). Entrepreneurship in climate governance at the local and regional levels: concepts, methods, patterns, and effects. *Regional Environmental Change*, 18, 1247-1257

3.1.3 Inclusive entrepreneurship

Different people engage in entrepreneurship for different reasons. As climate vulnerability varies based on social, economic, historic, and political factors⁴⁴, one might therefore expect that the climate adaptation solutions provided by entrepreneurs across these spectrums may vary. Indeed, vulnerable groups are anecdotally known to be more involved in environmental entrepreneurship and are innovating for adaptation in sustainable, inexpensive ways⁴⁵.

Entrepreneurs from different social groups also face different challenges. As highlighted in the introduction, female entrepreneurs in sub-Saharan Africa face different vulnerabilities and challenges to their businesses including in the face of climate change⁴⁶.

Providing representation of the diverse faces of entrepreneurship is critical to encourage diverse people to attempt entrepreneurship, particularly given the higher fear of failure and lower skill development often seen among women entrepreneurs⁴⁷. The government of Kenya is placing significant focus on supporting entrepreneurs from marginalised demographics (e.g., strengthening the managerial and technical capabilities of women who own small and medium enterprises under the Kenya Industry and Entrepreneurship Project⁴⁸); however, it's not clear whether its programmes to support entrepreneurs are designed to target the most pressing climate adaptation interests perceived by these groups through business.

3.2 Survey results

To provide a sense of the entrepreneurs in the sample and the aims of their businesses, survey results are first presented before qualitative interview data. The survey received 22 responses. As such, N=22 for all percentages unless otherwise stated.

3.2.1 Business types and products

The survey respondents were asked to identify the sector in which their business falls. Most of the respondents were either from the agriculture (36%) or energy (32%) sectors, with a minority from transport (14%) or other sectors.

Respondents were asked to list their top three products or services. Their responses are represented in a word cloud in Figure 2. The results are diverse. Common themes include solar and electric goods, pumps, pipes. These words point towards a common product - irrigation systems. The respondents were also asked for the prices of each of their main products and

⁴⁴ Thomas, K., Hardy, R. D., Lazrus, H., Mendez, M., Orlove, B., Rivera-Collazo, I., ... & Winthrop, R. (2019). Explaining differential vulnerability to climate change: A social science review. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 10(2), e565.

⁴⁵ Hörisch, J., Kollat, J. & Brieger, S.A. What influences environmental entrepreneurship? A multilevel analysis of the determinants of entrepreneurs' environmental orientation. *Small Bus Econ* 48, 47–69 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-016-9765-2>

⁴⁶ Gannon, Kate Elizabeth, et al. "The triple differential vulnerability of female entrepreneurs to climate risk in sub-Saharan Africa: Gendered barriers and enablers to private sector adaptation." *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change* 13.5 (2022): e793.

⁴⁷ Mersha, T., & Sriram, V. (2019). Gender, entrepreneurial characteristics, and success: Evidence from Ethiopia. *Thunderbird International Business Review*, 61(2), 157-167.

⁴⁸ Kenya Industry and Entrepreneurship Project. 2023. Project Beneficiaries. <http://www.kiep.go.ke/project-beneficiaries/>

their business. This indicates that the sample does align well with the target (i.e., climate change adaptation businesses) and that these businesses place high importance on this identity.

3.2.2 Business operations

We next asked about customer interactions and payment modalities. Respondents were asked to report how their clients pay for products or services. The most common payment methods were M-PESA (86%), cash (55%), and bank transfer (27%). Respondents were asked whether they received one-off or ongoing payments from their clients. 36% indicated that their payments were generally one-off, while 64% reported that they received ongoing payments.

We were also interested as to whether the businesses serve a particular demographic of clientele. To explore this on one demographic axis, respondents were asked to report or estimate what percentage of their clients are female. The average response was 44%.

We next asked a series of questions about employment. Respondents were asked how many people are employed currently in their business. 50% of respondents reported 10 employees or fewer (N=22). The full trend in Figure 4 follows exponential decay, with only one response above 100. Most of the businesses are therefore small. This makes sense, as the sample targeted entrepreneurs (i.e., typically early-stage businesses). Respondents were also asked to estimate how many jobs their business had created directly since it started. The trend was similar to their current employment counts. For instance, 50% still reported 10 or fewer jobs being created since the business had been started. However, four responses were above 100 jobs, compared to one response above 100 regarding current job counts.

Figure 4: The number of employees in the respondents' businesses (N=20).

We wanted to interrogate the demographics of the employees in the same way we looked at the demographics of the customers. The respondents were therefore asked to characterise their employees in terms of their full- or part-time status, managerial level, and gender. 75% respondents indicated that all their employees were full-time, while 25% had part-time employees as well (N=20). A 38% female workforce was reported amongst respondents on average⁵⁰ (N=16). Looking at their reported managerial positions, this raises slightly to 41%⁵¹ (N=17). Respondents were asked to estimate their employees' monthly wage and their own monthly wage. The results are plotted in Figure 5. Unsurprisingly, more employees than entrepreneurs fall into the lower income bracket.

Figure 5: Employee and entrepreneur wages (N=16).

3.3 Interview Results

Twenty two semi-structured interviews were conducted with entrepreneurs in the climate adaptation space in Nairobi, Kenya. These were the same respondents that completed the survey. Participants were from a range of business sectors in climate adaptation, namely e-mobility, renewable energy, agriculture, water management, waste management and retailing. Each interview took an average duration of one hour each. Table 1 shows an overview of sectors and products and the participants. Note that the participant names listed in Table 1 are fictitious names (i.e., pseudonyms) to maintain confidentiality.

We allowed participants to self-identify as an entrepreneur involved in climate adaptation. It can be argued that some of their business activities such as those in electric mobility align with mitigation alongside adaptation. However, we found the need to preserve their own perceptions

⁵⁰ Note that in data cleaning, two responses to this question had to be rejected, which indicated that more than 100% of the business' entire workforce were women. This reduced the sample size for this question.

⁵¹ Similarly, one respondent indicated a quantity of managers which was more than 100% of the business' entire workforce. This data point was rejected, reducing this question's sample size.

of what constitutes adaptation in this work as it allows us to understand the intrinsic motivation for running their businesses.

Table 1: Interview participants characteristics and pseudonyms.

#	Participant	Business Sectors	Products
1	Kithika	Renewable Energy	Ice and Cold Storage
2	Bahati	Agriculture	Drip irrigation technology, training smart agriculture
3	Amani	Electric Mobility	Electric Vehicles
4	Dala	Agricultural Retail	Agro-inputs e.g Technology, Information for farmers
5	Emeka	Renewable Energy	Electric Vehicles; Solar systems
6	Matheka	Electric Mobility	Battery swapping service and electric bikes
7	Sahara	Electric Mobility	Electric Buses and Financing
8	Biko	Waste Management	Biogas Technology
9	Duma	Agriculture	Vegetables
10	Asha	Agriculture	Virtual produce aggregation & information for farmers
11	Gitonga	Renewable Energy	Energy Management Systems & Solar technology
12	Lule	Waste Management	Biogas Systems
13	Gathii	Food Retail	Retail Logistics, Groceries
14	Juma	Water Management	Prepaid Water Systems
15	Kiio	Electric Mobility	Electric Bicycles
16	Ekwee	Electric Mobility	Electric Motorbikes
17	Ngina	Biotechnology	Fertilizer & Insect Protein e.g. crickets and black soldier flies
18	Sulati	Biotechnology	Fertilizer & Insect Protein e.g. black soldier flies,
19	Luna	Renewable Energy	Solar systems, smart monitoring devices
20	Mwendwa	Agriculture	Beehives, honey
21	Sauda	Waste Management	Art
22	Mueni	Agriculture	Eggs

The varying ways in which entrepreneurs self-defined as tackling climate adaptation speaks to how diverse adaptation can look. What may look like mitigation to some may be perceived as adaptation to others. This also speaks to the context-specificity of adaptation - adaptation measures may look like “patchwork adjustments across space”⁵².

In each of the following subsections, key themes are first presented in a table alongside exemplary quotes, and later discussed in detail. A combined table of all key findings is provided in Appendix D.

⁵² Mendelsohn, R. (2012). The economics of adaptation to climate change in developing countries. *Climate Change Economics*, 3(02), 1250006.

3.3.1 Motivation of Entrepreneurs

Participants were asked to share their motivations for starting a business in the climate adaptation space. Through the coding and thematic analysis process described in the Methods, five main motivations were identified: (1) identification of gaps or issues; (2) knowledge of existing solutions; (3) desire to bring local solutions; (4) desire to provide affordable solutions; and (5) ideals for a better life. These are listed and illustrated via sample quotes in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Key motivations emerging from the interviews and illustrative quotes.

Motivation	Exemplary Quote
Identification of gaps or issues	<i>"Being in the energy space, I saw a gap where commercial and industrial companies are able to afford and are able to incorporate renewable energy into their operations, yet there was a lack of solutions that are addressing rural communities [...]. So we saw that gap and thought we should be able to find a model where the rural communities can be able to increase their incomes and quality of life by having solutions that are powered by renewable energy" (Kithika, Renewable Energy)</i>
Knowledge of existing solutions in the international market	<i>"Being in Africa, we also recognize that we are at the tail end of most of these discussions. Because if you see countries like the UK, Germany, Japan, China, they have already transitioned towards electric mobility. But normally for Africa we need to wait for something to be trained outside before it comes in." (Amani, Electric Mobility)</i>
Desire to bring locally designed and appropriate solutions	<i>"We wanted to develop local technology, because when we came into the market we were like, okay, let's see, are there solutions in the market? And why are they not working? And one aspect that we found out was that the technology was quite expensive. So, technology's been on the market, but not affordable to people that should be able to take up these solutions." (Biko, Waste Management)</i>
Desire to reduce costs for consumers using climate-friendly approaches	<i>"The major problem was that farming fish is very expensive in Kenya due to the feed that is available. So, she started researching that and then based on that, she found out that the feed is too expensive because of the protein components. So, she was like, instead of me joining the problem, let me try to fix the problem." (Ngina, Biotechnology)</i>
Desire to provide products or services which align with ideals for a better life	<i>"My biggest motivation was to understand where food was coming from in order to make better decisions for the health of my family and I, and then that very quickly developed into the health of the planet as well, because of course, they're so closely interconnected." (Gathii, Food Retail)</i>

The first theme is the identification of gaps or issues relating to existing climate change issues. All the entrepreneurs cited gaps in the climate adaptation market as a motivation to venture into business. Some had also identified pure market gaps between supply and demand: for instance, one interviewee in bee-keeping cited that Kenya had five times more honey demand than supply, which motivated their business, as illustrated in the following quote:

"We have five times the demand of honey in this market as opposed to supply which is very unusual, because in Agri-business, you will have a lot of produce and not so many consumers. Here, we have so many consumers and not enough produce. So I was motivated to find out what's going on." (Mwendwa, Agriculture)

However, the gaps were not all simply driven by a supply-demand imbalance. In rural areas they identified energy service and market access gaps which affect quality of life and income for farmers, and wanted to help meet those needs, as illustrated in the following quote.

“Being in the energy space, I saw a gap where commercial and industrial companies are able to afford and are able to incorporate renewable energy into their operations, yet there was a lack of solutions that are addressing rural communities. And that is where most of the produce that commercial and industrial food chains rely on. So we saw that gap and thought we should be able to find a model where the rural communities can be able to increase their incomes and quality of life by having solutions that are powered by renewable energy to enable them” (Kithika, Renewable Energy).

Some entrepreneurs perceived gaps in the agricultural sector in the rural areas that had knock-on effects on food security more broadly throughout Kenya. They were therefore motivated to improve food security by supporting local farmers. This extended not only to service provision but to reduction of post-harvest waste, creating two-birds-one-stone effects by improving food security and increasing rural income.

“We could go and see so much food going to waste especially in Kirinyaga where there is production of tomatoes. Most of these farmers throw away these tomatoes but then with zero market for the tomato. So, we had to think of a way we can be able to handle this for current growth.” (Asha, Agriculture)

Meanwhile in urban areas, entrepreneurs identified waste management and mobility service gaps which were negatively affecting their desired consumer base. They aimed to fill these gaps to create a cleaner and more pleasant environment, and thereby provide value to their customers. This is illustrated for the case of waste management in the following quote:

“I think I was initially pushed by the fact that we have serious environmental issues in this country in terms of managing our waste. Our sewage coverage stands at around 29 in Nairobi but countrywide we are at around 12%. So, meaning that we have very serious issues to do with managing our waste in the urban areas. And one thing that hit me when I came to Nairobi was, the place that I moved to had sewage overflowing everywhere in the streets and all that. When I checked our rivers, they were choking with waste. So, that became my drive. I said that I’ll take it upon myself to figure out and find a solution” (Biko, Waste Management).

Some of the entrepreneurs were motivated by their knowledge of existing solutions to these gaps which originate from other international markets. They wanted to bring these solutions to the local market, expressing impatience with waiting for the solutions to arrive otherwise. They conveyed a perception that Kenya, and Africa more broadly, is somewhat behind the times despite strong natural resources and market potential, as illustrated in the following quotes: .

“Being in Africa, we also recognize that we are at the tail end of most of these discussions. Because if you see countries like the UK, Germany, Japan, China, they have already transitioned towards electric mobility. But normally for Africa we need to wait for something to be trained out outside before it comes in. Even though the whole climate change affects us, basically, equally, so we thought starting something now that will be running concurrently that was running out, it would be very interesting, especially

for our clients who are looking to have sustainable production, sustainable workplaces, and basically reducing their carbon footprint, we thought it would be interesting for us to provide a solution for and also give out cars that are slightly cheaper to run but what they're really have right now ” (Amani, Electric Mobility).

“I have a Co-founder. He went to Israel and when he came back into the country, we met and he told me about how Israel is able to achieve so much agricultural output whilst being in a desert, and he noted that Kenya receives more rainfall, has higher plot coverage, and has a more agricultural background than Israel, So why can't we replicate what they do in Kenya before it's too late? And why can't we sort farming issues in arid and semi-arid lands when Israel has been able to do it? That is really the main inspiration; if a desert can do it: produce globally recognized vegetable produce (fruits), why can't we do it?” (Bahati, Agriculture).

However, other participants recognised adaptation gaps where importing international solutions directly would not work: a locally appropriate solution was needed. These entrepreneurs were motivated to create unique local solutions to the gaps that they had identified in the market, either through customisation of international technologies or home-grown local innovations. For instance, one entrepreneur developed an innovative local solution to the problem of unaffordable protein-rich fish feed through insect-based low-carbon feed:

“So, the person who founded the company comes from an agricultural background. When she came back to Kenya, she wanted to start growing fish, because that was supposed to be the next upcoming protein when it comes to human consumption. But then as she was looking into the fish farming industry, she stumbled across some problems of which the major problem was that farming fish is very expensive in Kenya due to the feed that is available. So, she started researching that and then based on that, she found out that the feed is too expensive because of the protein components. So, she was like, instead of me joining the problem, let me try to fix the problem. And that's kind of how [business name] started. So, the solution that she found for that specific problem was insects, so from there kind of the mission was born where we try to farm a better world with the help of insects ” (Ngina, Biotechnology).

This example points towards a key constraint which rendered existing technologies in international markets impractical to many of these entrepreneurs: affordability. Several entrepreneurs perceived that, while there were relevant clean technologies on the broader market, they simply were not affordable to the average Kenyan consumer. So, they considered how they could be re-designed in different ways to increase affordability. An example of this is illustrated in the quote below in the sector of waste management.

“We wanted to develop local technology, because when we came into the market we were like, okay, let's see, are there solutions in the market? And why are they not working? And one aspect that we found out was that the technology was quite expensive. So, technology's been on the market, but not affordable to people that should be able to take up these solutions. So, you find now for apartments to manage their

waste water, there are just shortcuts, because they have a fear of high expense of managing their waste. What do they do? They have to dispose of it into the environment. So that they can cut down their costs. So, we came in, like, Okay, we have a solution here. It's quite affordable in terms of installation, operation and maintenance. So, it's quite friendly. And in our journey in terms of building the product, we developed it with the apartment owners. The people that had the problem are the people that funded the research and gave us an opportunity to experiment with our solutions on their premises“ (Biko, Waste Management).

It is thus not surprising to note that some entrepreneurs perceived that consumers were not motivated by the inherent benefit of climate adaptation but by the financial relief adaptation activities can bring. Many of the consumers in the entrepreneurs' target markets are in strained financial situations, and ergo the entrepreneurs were often motivated to start their businesses not to use climate-friendly technologies for the environment's sake, but to improve affordability of key services and cost of living for their consumers.

“I came to realise that the motivation of most clients who put solar panels is never about the environment. It's usually mainly about saving money, not the environment. Most of the clients don't really care too much, they want to lower their electric bill, not to keep paying Kenya power. So they're looking at it on their financial basis ” (Luna, Renewable Energy).

Finally, beyond the needs of their *consumers* and availability of solutions, some were motivated by their *own* intrinsic ideals. They perceived ways their communities or lives could be better in an ideal, climate-friendly world and wanted to enact that change through business. These ideals include, for instance, the desire for organic produce and cleaner air. Their desire to meet these desired and envisioned higher standards of living based on their own lived experiences led them to join the sector, as illustrated in the following quotes.

“My biggest motivation was to understand where food was coming from in order to make better decisions for the health of my family and I, and then that very quickly developed into the health of the planet as well, because of course, they're so closely interconnected” (Gathii, Food Retail).

“Remember, in 2020, when we had COVID?. So you will realise that, at that time, the transport system was shut down. And mostly activities around human beings were shut down, movements were limited. We were able to see Mount Kenya, clearly from Nairobi. The sky was so clear, it was so clean, we're breathing fresh air. So this really motivated us to actually impact the environment, especially the urban transport by providing clean transport, where we minimise the exhaust emissions” (Emeka, Renewable Energy)

3.3.2 Perception of Business Impact

The entrepreneurs were asked to discuss the social, economic and environmental impacts of their climate adaptation businesses. The key impacts that emerged are listed and illustrated via

sample quotes in Table 3 below. They can be generally categorised as either environmental, economic, or social impacts.

Table 3: Key business impacts emerging from the interviews.

Theme	Impact	Exemplary Quote
Environmental	Reduction of pollution	<i>"The first impact we have made is on the environment, and no pollution, no noise pollution or air pollution, removing carbon from the atmosphere." (Sahara, Electric Mobility).</i>
	Water conservation	<i>"The more water is wasted in non-productive ways, the more we are affecting the climate [...] the best way is about to look at how we can use the little water that we have because water as a resource, it's never enough and guard it" (Juma, Water Management).</i>
	Forest conservation	<i>"Well, saving forests is the main impact. So, for us, we are providing a cooking solution or an energy solution that will stop people from cutting down trees" (Lule, Waste Management).</i>
Economic	Affordable and quality products in the market	<i>"So, insects are a component of animal feed. So, it helps in replacement of soya and silver fish. So, it replaces other existing protein components of which we aim that insects are more stable in price and quality, which is often the problem in Kenya" (Ngina, Biotechnology).</i>
	Increased agricultural output	<i>"We see amazing results with the fertiliser, like people double or triple their output for a year, as well as reduce the use of pesticides." (Ngina, Biotechnology).</i>
	Decreased (post-harvest) food and water wastage	<i>"So we provide cold storage and ice to fishers who then are able to go for longer fishing expeditions using the ice and then what this does is that it reduces post-harvest losses because you're able to maintain the quality of the fish from when it is caught to the landing sites to the processing facility." (Kithika, Renewable Energy).</i>
	Increased income and resources	<i>"By providing better prices for the Fisher-folks, then increasing their climate resilience because there's a lot more income they may be able to diversify to other economic activities and reduce their total reliance on just fishing as a source of income" (Kithika, Renewable Energy).</i>
	Inclusion of the youth and the low income earners in the labour force	<i>"The main impact that we are aiming to create in the long term is to have as many youths as possible getting into agriculture, more specifically into the agricultural value chain. So, the average age of the farmer currently is 57 years and over 75% of our population is below 35 years. So what happens when the current farmers disappear, so to speak? We'll have a generation that does not know how to produce food" (Bahati, Agriculture).</i>
Social	Provision of solutions to the underprivileged in society	<i>"And also probably another impact is [...] ideally bridging the gap and also tapping all the untapped opportunities regarding to the rural holders because majority of the companies are working with people in urban areas, but we thought who is taking care of the rural farmers" (Dala, Agricultural Retail).</i>
	Education of the customer on matters relating to climate change	<i>"Conversation that climate change is actually happening, and what can we do actively towards mitigating that and solutions that are working outside also the same the solutions that will work here, like if I take out your Prado and give you an electric vehicle, what sort of things would you benefit from." (Amani, Electric Mobility).</i>

Environmental Impacts:

The entrepreneurs reported numerous types of ongoing environmental impact. For instance, some discussed conservation (e.g., of water or forests) as illustrated in the quote below.

“Well, saving forests is the main impact. So, for us, we are providing a cooking solution or an energy solution that will stop people from cutting down trees” (Lule, Waste Management).

These entrepreneurs’ impacts are preventative: they work to prevent future harm by conserving existing carbon sinks and natural resources. Entrepreneurs who aimed to create an impact in pollution reduction also worked preventatively, envisioning themselves as removing future carbon from the atmosphere.

“The first impact we have made is on the environment, and no pollution, no noise pollution or air pollution, removing carbon from the atmosphere” (Sahara, Electric Mobility).

Other entrepreneurs were trying to create impact not by preventing harm but instead by reversing or mitigating ongoing damage. For instance entrepreneurs in the waste sector sought to reverse or mitigate existing unmanaged waste:

“We want to help mitigate the impact of unmanaged waste on the environment and carbon emissions. We want to recover some of these resources in terms of creating clean sources of energy for households in urban areas, thus also mitigating the effects of climate change” (Biko, Waste Management).

Not all businesses had achieved their intended environmental impact by the time we interviewed them. Some of the environmental impacts were seemingly still aspirational based on how they phrased their statement. An example of this is illustrated in the following quote.

“I think the immediate impact that we wanted to really realise first of all is that I dream of clean rivers, rivers without waste. That is one of the biggest things I am looking forward to hopefully changing in the coming years” (Biko, Waste Management).

Economic Impact:

The majority of the respondents felt that their businesses and market offerings were either contributing or aspiring to contribute to economic growth. First, entrepreneurs perceived that they were creating impact by providing affordable and quality products in the market. They see this as a way to create economic impact for their consumers, as illustrated in the following quote:

“So, insects are a component of animal feed. So, it helps in replacement of soya and silver fish. So, it replaces other existing protein components of which we aim that insects are more stable in price and quality, which is often the problem in Kenya” (Ngina, Biotechnology).

Another key economic impact that respondents described was increased agricultural output. By providing products such as fertilisers to increase farm yields, they created impact by both improving incomes and building food security:.

“The company has only existed for five years. Yeah, not very, but for us, because it's such a new industry, what the exact impact is, it's still very hard to see. But we see amazing results with the fertiliser, like people double or triple their output for a year, as well as reduce the use of pesticides” (Ngina, Biotechnology).

Others took a different approach to creating economic impact: instead of increasing output, they aimed to reduce waste and improve efficiency. This is illustrated for the case of reducing (post-harvest) food wastage in the following quotes

“So we provide cold storage and ice to fishers who then are able to go for longer fishing expeditions using the ice and then what this does is that it reduces post-harvest losses because you're able to maintain the quality of the fish from when it is caught to the landing sites to the processing facility” (Kithika, Renewable Energy).

“Main impact is to improve or reduce the poverty levels among the farmers and also to reduce the post harvest losses” (Asha, Agriculture).

Many of these economic impacts intersect with social impact. They allow growth of the economy by increasing incomes, which provides people the economic leverage to meet more of their social needs. This is illustrated in the following quote with regards to diversification of incomes for fishing communities:

“By providing better prices for the Fisher-folks, then increasing their climate resilience because there's a lot more income they may be able to diversify to other economic activities and reduce their total reliance on just fishing as a source of income. The extra income can also be used by families to educate their children, which actually helps them. For example, if fishing were to be affected by climate change, They'll be able to generate income from other sources as well and use education as a tool for future income generation” (Kithika, Renewable Energy).

The innovative technologies these entrepreneurs provide can directly improve both micro- and macro-economic status in consumer communities. One particularly direct example of this came from an entrepreneur whose technological design simply and effectively prevented theft and thereby increased income, simply due to its weight and lockability:

“There are people who like stealing beehives because they are, they have a ready market. But now our hives, one is about 100 kilos, nobody steals it because that is going to be a weightlifter there is just no way of putting it on your shoulders. So that is one thing that has worked well for us. And then we went ahead to make the hive lockable. So there is a place where you can actually place a padlock such that nobody interferes with your beehive in that kind of a situation. So much innovation in just one product.” (Mwendwa, Agriculture)

Another economic impact that intersects with social impact is the growth of the labour force through the inclusion of the youth and the low income earners. Entrepreneurs aimed to bring

youth into farming, renewable energy, and other green sectors to both grow food security and reduce Kenya's high youth unemployment rate⁵³, as illustrated in the following quotes:

“The main impact that we are aiming to create in the long term is to have as many youths as possible getting into agriculture, more specifically into the agricultural value chain. So, the average age of the farmer currently is 57 years and over 75% of our population is below 35 years. So what happens when the current farmers disappear, so to speak? We'll have a generation that does not know how to produce food and at least based on international standards one farmer doing something large scale should be able to produce food for 140 people” (Bahati, Agriculture)

“So number one impact was that we were aiming at, you realise that in Kenya, over a period of time, there are so many youths who are unemployed, and we wanted to give them an alternative solution, where they can create their own income” (Emeka, Renewable Energy).

Social Impact:

Regarding social impact, a few of the sampled entrepreneurs spoke about the intentional provision of the solutions to the underprivileged in society. They discussed how their products benefit vulnerable groups such as rural farmers, and their business strategies intentionally focus on them as customers, as illustrated in the following quote:

“Majority of the companies are working with people in urban areas, but we thought who is taking care of the rural farmers and the Agro-holders as so we thought of impacting where we come from mostly because we all have ancestry in, in rural areas.” (Dala, Agricultural Retail)

The entrepreneurs also discussed building business models that enable these vulnerable groups to provide the products or offerings affordably, thereby enabling access. These include cross-subsidy (i.e., by extending water systems not only to meet richer customers but also poorer ones, enabling access at a marginal cost increase) and dual benefit (i.e., creating both energy and water access benefits via solar water pumping systems).

“One of the biggest ways we are serving the less-served than privileged, remember looking at, for example, that village, there are two extremes here. One person is able to drill a borehole and equip it. And that is how he happened to have water growth in his home. But the next neighbour doesn't have a tap. The reason why they don't have a tap even with the motivation of having one, because they can see how it is working, is because they cannot manage it. So, when you talk to this one investor and he agrees to supply the rest of the neighbours with water, that way we are serving the less fortunate and the underserved. You see, when these people do not have clean, portable water, it means they will end up consuming water from the streams and other low sources. But

⁵³ <https://www.fke-kenya.org/policy-issues/youth-employment>

you see, borehole water is cleaner and when it is treated, it's completely portable, and is safe for drinking. So, when we provide safer water, it would mean that we are eliminating water borne diseases ” (Juma, Water Management)

“We are dealing with the issue of water scarcity. So with our solar water pumping solutions, we are not only giving people who have access to electricity and are trying to lower their bills, we are also giving a solution to people who do not have grid access in their areas or ability to track the water from underground to use up and those are the biggest in terms of water supply for most people. That is, the people who are not close to lakes or things of the sort, the highest amount of water you can be able to generate is from underground aquifers. So for solar pumping solutions, now people from all regions can be able to access water from the underground aquifers and be able to do it using sustainable means” (Luna, Renewable Energy).

One respondent uniquely stated that their societal contribution was in the education of the customer on matters relating to climate change and their role in mitigating it. In this way, the entrepreneur was both building awareness and building their business, creating two-birds-one-stone impact.

“Majorly conversation, conversation that climate change is actually happening, and what can we do actively towards mitigating that and solutions that are working outside also the same the solutions that will work here, like if I take out your Prado and give you an electric vehicle, what sort of things would you benefit from” (Amani, Electric Mobility).

Finally, entrepreneurs in the agriculture and food spaces often aimed to create a broader impact of food security spanning society at large. Their reasoning for this impact highlighted the interconnectedness of all three categories of impact (i.e., social, economic, and environmental), as shown in the following quotes

“The main impact I meant for starting this business was to establish a resilient agricultural model that adapts to climate challenges by promoting sustainable farming practices. I intend to enhance food security, support local communities and contribute to the overall stability of the agricultural sector in the face of changing environmental conditions” (Duma, Agriculture)

“Now we work with a lot of smallholder farmers. And what we're demonstrating to the farming community is that there is a route to market where customers care, and will appreciate what effort is going into growing fruit and vegetables organically and in a way that's going to protect their soil. ... the impact that I like to have is to really change the food systems and demonstrate that it's viable to run a business like this where you put people on the planet and the same level of importance as profit” (Gathii, Food Retail).

3.3.3 Climate Adaptation Needs Addressed

Entrepreneurs were asked to identify the key climate needs they were addressing. The key needs that emerged are listed in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Key climate adaptation needs emerging from the interviews.

Need	Exemplary Quote
Reducing greenhouse gas emissions	<i>"Air pollution is seen by the emission of combustion gases, greenhouse gases, just from the internal combustion that happens inside the engine. So, these electric buses [...] they do not emit those gases into the atmosphere." (Sahara, Electric Mobility).</i>
Provision of affordable and clean energy	<i>"We are really campaigning for renewable energies. I would say it's campaigning on educating clients or potential clients on the advantages of adopting renewable energy technologies, especially the farmers who are using diesel generators. You know there are so many farmers who use diesel generators. These generators are polluting rivers. We try as much as possible to replace those diesel water pumps with solar water pumps" (Gitonga, Renewable Energy).</i>
Provision of secondary economic opportunities for those in climate-vulnerable sectors	<i>"Our bikes are easy bikes, they use battery, and this can be charged from either solar or electricity directly from the grid. So that means that we are promoting the use of energy, clean renewable energy and then at the same time solving the aspects of affordability really in the climate space, and that means our low-income earners can get extra money because our bike is cheaper to operate" (Ekwee, Electric Mobility).</i>
Resilience in agricultural inputs and practices	<i>"Firstly, my business is employing efficient irrigation methods to counteract the impact of scarce rains. And secondly, my business is also utilising seeds specifically designed to thrive in dry conditions. These measures enhance the resilience of agricultural operations of my business. Ultimately, ensuring productivity even in the face of variable and challenging climate patterns." (Duma, Agriculture).</i>
Managing Waste	<i>"The biggest one there is reduction. Like now a lot of the organic waste is dumped. And there are already more and more movements on like, what can we do with the waste? So, I think for us we collect waste, and we make it into valuable products so that definitely reduces emissions" (Ngina, Biotechnology)</i>

One of the top needs that entrepreneurs aimed to address was reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Interestingly, they framed this as an adaptation need and not as a mitigation need, often relating greenhouse gas emissions to air quality and pollution. The entrepreneurs were tackling this need in various ways. Some discussed creating solutions that utilised clean energy (e.g., for electric transport) while others created products that directly contributed to the reduction of deforestation through the use of alternative raw materials (e.g., through the construction of non-traditional concrete beehives). These examples are illustrated in the following quotes:

"The second climate pollution we are mitigating is air pollution. Air pollution is seen by the emission of combustion gases, greenhouse gases, just from the internal combustion that happens inside the engine. So, these electric buses they do not have agents so, they do not emit those gases into the atmosphere. And looking at an apple to apples comparison of a non-combustion engine bus and electric bus and electric bus in a year would produce up to between one and two tonnes of carbon annually. diesel bus would produce between 40 and 50 tonnes of carbon annually. No comparison at all." (Sahara, Electric Mobility).

"We are saying don't cut trees anymore to make beehives, use an alternative material that is lasting a lifetime of 80, 90, 100 years. So get it from me; the moment you have a set of six hives, you have cut a tree. In four years, you have to cut another tree to maintain the hives that have been worn out, four years. So in 100 years, you will have cut 25 trees to just sustain a set of six hives. And the other way is when you have six

hives that are lasting you 100 years, then you have been able to save all these 25 trees from being cut. And now the funniest thing is also the fact that a tree absorbs about 21 kilos of carbon every year. So you can multiply 25 trees absorbing 21 kilos of carbon for 100 years. That's about 52 tonnes of carbon. So the six hives have been able to save mother nature 52.5 tons of carbon from being emitted directly. But remember, one tree you know, they drop the seeds and stuff like that, a tree is able to reproduce itself to about 500 seedlings, but about 10% of those survive into trees, so whenever you cut a tree, you cut a tree and pass the trees into reproduction, are you seeing? So us, we are saving the tree, and its children. It's actually monumental, it's actually crazy. So the amount of impact we are actually having on nature in terms of saving the mother nature, it's amazing. So we are saving 52.5 tonnes of carbon from only six sets of concrete hives, by prevention of emission and all the other things that come with not cutting the trees in terms of the bags of air, in terms of soil erosion, in terms of medicine, because these trees, they also provide medicine to us" (Mwendwa, Agriculture).

"So, ideally, we are trying to reduce global warming or the global effect that is as a result of air pollution. And just like I described earlier, you realise that, from the data that already exists, there are so many emissions that are created by the diesel power the engine vehicles and also the fuel powered engine two wheelers. So, by producing these units, a vehicle at a time, we are trying to reduce these carbon emissions, so that we create a friendly environment and try to reduce the global effect you have seen the effect that the global warming can cause in terms of climate change, you realise that prolonged droughts, we realised that we are experiencing sporadic rainfalls. And through bringing up these products, we are trying to actually address this problem and we believe that our sales together with other players who are also in the market will greatly reduce the global effect" (Emeka, Renewable Energy).

Many of the respondents state that one of the main needs that they are addressing is the provision of affordable and clean energy. This is an interesting concept, as entrepreneurs in sectors like e-mobility or solar irrigation may often be more strongly associated with the physical technologies and services they provide (i.e., transport and irrigation) and less about the underlying energy which enables them. However, these entrepreneurs spoke about affordable and clean energy, and awareness of this, as a key part of their model.

"As a business I would say we are really campaigning for renewable energies. I would say it's campaigning on educating clients or potential clients on the advantages of adopting renewable energy technologies, especially the farmers who are using diesel generators. You know there are so many farmers who use diesel generators. These generators are polluting rivers. We try as much as possible to replace those diesel water pumps with solar water pumps" (Gitonga, Renewable Energy).

While meeting these needs, entrepreneurs are also meeting the need for secondary economic opportunities and income sources amongst those in climate vulnerable industries. This is particularly interesting in the e-mobility space. While e-mobility is often seen as a mitigation

sector, one respondent argued its case as an adaptation sector by explaining how e-bikes, being easy and cheaper to operate, can provide a second source of income for low-income earners in climate-volatile sectors such as agriculture. By creating this secondary source of income, the e-mobility sector can therefore be seen as increasing resilience and adaptive capacity.

“Our bikes are easy bikes, they use battery, and this can be charged from either solar or electricity directly from the grid. So that means that we are promoting the use of energy, clean renewable energy and then at the same time solving the aspects of affordability really in the climate space, and that means our low-income earners can get extra money because our bike is cheaper to operate” (Ekwee, Electric Mobility).

Some respondents also reported providing products and methods that enable farmers to be more resilient in their agricultural businesses, hence ensuring food security. Respondents discussed how farmers need to adapt to scarce rains, depleted soil, dirty rivers, and extreme heat via the use of climate resilient seeds, improved fertilisers, water services, and bee-protecting hives, as illustrated in the quotes below.

“Firstly, my business is employing efficient irrigation methods to counteract the impact of scarce rains. And secondly, my business is also utilising seeds specifically designed to thrive in dry conditions. These measures enhance the resilience of agricultural operations of my business. Ultimately, ensuring productivity even in the face of variable and challenging climate patterns” (Duma, Agriculture)

“Some of the people that are really affected by climate change are farmers, and they are the people that we are focusing on really helping in terms of boosting their production, improving soil health. By tapping into organic fertilisers, taking it back to the farmers who is able to revitalise, rebuild the soil and make it productive again so that these adverse climatic conditions which are really affecting production, we’re able to help them adapt to some of these changes also water is one scarce resource that has been used over the years. So, by recreating clean rivers and turning our urban areas into clean sources of rivers to downstream consumers who majorly also are farmers. We are helping to provide water that they can use for the provision of farms” (Biko, Waste Management).

“So, the adaptation is two way, the bees are having to adapt well in our beehives, because generally temperatures have risen across this continent. But our hives are cool inside. So the bees are not suffering the extreme heat they’ll be suffering in a wooden hive because of the insulation. And you see for the bees, about 80% of the food we eat in Africa is pollinated mainly by the bees. And so if we don’t take care of our bees and nurture them, we don’t have a lot of foodstuffs in the fields, but we have nobody to pollinate them. So the yields are going down and down and down because we don’t have enough bees. So the more we make the bees adaptable by having a concrete beehive, which is heat insulated, the bees are able to reproduce even more because they’re happy” (Mwendwa, Agriculture).

Some respondents stated that managing waste is one of the climate adaptation needs that they are addressing through their businesses. Again, this may often be seen as mitigation instead of adaptation, but these entrepreneurs self-identified as involved in adaptation. Most of them were recycling waste (e.g., organic waste, fuel oils) to either create new products or reuse it rather than dump it, as illustrated in the following quotes. This speaks to circular economy opportunities in their sectors.

“The biggest one there is reduction. Like now a lot of the organic waste is dumped. And there are already more and more movements on like, what can we do with the waste? So, I think for us we collect waste, and we make it into valuable products so that definitely reduces emissions” (Ngina, Biotechnology)

“We are able to reuse used engine oils, instead of being poured on the soil to pollute our soil, we are using it in our concrete hive in our device, the Kaluki guard, to mix it with water and prevent black ants, safari ants and white ants from climbing on top. We say, don't pour it on the ground, give it to us and then it's not even evaporating to the environment. The guard is such that it prevents evaporation, it is just maintained there. We arrest it there. So that's another big thing. And so it's helping conserve our soils and conserve our food” (Mwendwa, Agriculture).

3.3.4 Underlying Values

The interview text was coded using the UPV value framework wherever the entrepreneurs discussed values in relation to their business motivations and impacts (i.e., questions 22, 23, and 24 in Appendix A). This particular set of codes was analysed quantitatively by frequency to identify the most common values that entrepreneurs employ when discussing their business. Please refer to the full codes list in Appendix B, which indicates the UPV values being studied.

The top values are listed in descending order in Figure 4 below. The most frequently mentioned values are ‘innovation’ (9%) and ‘entrepreneurship’ (7%). This is unsurprising given the context and focus of the interviews. The next most highly discussed value is ‘preservation of the natural environment’ (7%), which clearly relates to the climate adaptation aims of the respondents’ businesses such as pollution reduction and waste management. The next most highly discussed values are ‘accessibility to services’ (5%), ‘being informed’ (5%), and ‘caring for others’ (4%). These values show the importance of the entrepreneurs’ relationship. It is only at this point in the list which the value ‘income’ finally emerges (4%).

Figure 4: Top values discussed by entrepreneurs in relation to their businesses.

3.3.5 Challenges experienced

Respondents also discussed challenges they were experiencing. The key emerging challenges are shown in Table 5. Generally, these challenges align with barriers identified in the literature⁵⁴.

Table 5: Key challenges emerging from the interviews.

Challenge	Exemplary quote
Access to appropriate finance	<i>“Currently there’s a lot of financing for climate related products. Well, that financing is not available to low-income individuals. Like the financing itself is for SMEs and above. The youths and the women who are disadvantaged, unless they are in those government initiatives for disability, they won’t get the financing. Because the financing is based on the company, the financial documents that you have. You need to submit bank statements. The financing to low-income earners is very hard” (Gitonga, Renewable Energy).</i>
Lack of technical capacity	<i>“Well, the biggest risk is the limited knowledge base that we have with the current team. So yes, we have an agronomist, yes, we have someone handling the production process, but these are people who’ve had on the job training and do not really have the technical expertise to be able to do that [...]. My colleague co-founder is a Biosystems engineer [...] but there’s always things that are really beyond our scope of knowledge.” (Sulati, Biotechnology).</i>
Lack of consumer and regulator awareness	<i>“The products that you’re coming up with, sometimes people are a bit concerned. Just on the issue on basis of; Is this thing safe? Can I use biogas that has been produced from poop? How safe is this water if I am eating vegetables that have been grown from recycled water? So, it is a big risk in terms of how people will accept these projects. Will people support these projects?” (Biko, Waste Management).</i>

⁵⁴ Pauw, P., & Pegels, A. (2013). Private sector engagement in climate change adaptation in least developed countries: An exploration. *Climate and Development*, 5(4), 257–267.

<p>Unfriendly taxation and licensing policies</p>	<p><i>"The other thing is licensing and taxation, Where the government has policies relating to licensing and taxation. For you to acquire licences and install our contractors. There are other documents that are very much needed. You have to submit the permits from the county, you have to submit a compliance certificate, you have to pay an application fee, you have to pay a client fee. You need to have a business, you need to have affidavits, you need to have a lease or title deed. When you compile all those costs, they are very high. It's a hindrance to turning knowledge into practice into business." (Gitonga, Renewable Energy).</i></p>
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A key challenge across the vast majority of entrepreneurs was found to be **access to appropriate finance**. Entrepreneurs in climate adaptation sectors need patient capital, grants, and loans. Patience is key as research and development is often needed in cutting-edge climate technologies before deployment; immediate returns cannot therefore be expected, as illustrated in quote below.

"Our biggest challenge was actually financing, and its financing towards development of these devices that we are developing, the ones that we prototype. So these devices will be significantly a game changer because we are automating everything, where we can be able to check the status of your pump, we can be able to troubleshoot for everyone, and anyone in this space can also be able to do that, to be able to provide consultancy services for that. So that was our next big goal and we're requesting financing for development of these devices. Yes, and the main reason we did not go with the loan option is that this money is not going towards purchasing something that will bring money back directly. That money is going towards research and development and testing of something, such that we're able to get financing and be able to significantly develop these devices" (Luna, Renewable Energy).

However, patient capital is not readily available. As reported by the following interviewee, minimal capital is available, and that which is available is neither cheap enough nor patient for entrepreneurs in this sector:

"This is a business, this needs to be highly capitalised, highly injection of money. So that's a challenge. And, you know, number one, capital is not cheap, capital is not readily available, and capital may sometimes not be patient" (Sahara, Electric Mobility)

To bridge this finance gap, impact investors and venture capitalists are one option, but accessing these funds requires business acumen (i.e., the knowledge on how to write a proposal, pitch) and financial literacy. Additionally, such investors tend to invest in large businesses the scale of which most small entrepreneurs cannot meet. This is illustrated by the following interviewee quote about inaccessibility of capital to vulnerable entrepreneurs:

"Currently there's a lot of financing for climate related products. Well, that financing is not available to low-income individuals. Like the financing itself is for SMEs and above. The youths and the women who are disadvantaged, unless they are in those government initiatives for disability, they won't get the financing. Because the financing is based on the company, the financial documents that you have. You need to submit bank statements. The financing to low-income earners is very hard" (Gitonga, Renewable Energy).

Addressing the skills and knowledge gaps through setting up supportive business and innovation ecosystems that help coordinate entrepreneurs, channel funding opportunities and also offer mentorships and training is key to addressing these barriers. There is a clear need for financial institutions to design instruments tailored to this growing market and for training to access these instruments in order to allow climate adaptation businesses to scale.

“The bigger challenge is scaling up. Yeah, because I can give you a few statistics. For example, we realise that our bike is in the pipeline to South Africa. Around 500 pieces, you realise it's around 1000 pieces needed in Rwanda locally this year, we need to produce around 8000 bikes there is demand everywhere. And we are not able to actually meet this demand because of financial constraints” (Emeka, Renewable Energy).

There are also challenges around a **lack of technical capacity** that is limiting business growth. Entrepreneurs in the climate space seem to stem from diverse backgrounds: some start these businesses due to knowledge and passion around particular technologies, whereas others are business specialists without the technical know-how. This can be illustrated through comparison of quotes from two interviewees:

“So after working there for a couple of months, I went back to the US and was really interested in learning more about solar systems and solar energy. So I did a lot of research, talked to people there about systems and everything.” (Luna, Renewable Energy)

“So I love to do business. And I understood business but I also wanted to innovate something. So for me, I had a deep inspiration within me to be known for a certain solution” (Mwendwa, Agriculture)

These two entrepreneurs were motivated to work in this space for very different reasons: one due to a technical interest in solar, and one due to a passion for business. They bring different skill-sets to the table, and need to find relevant counterparts to round out their company's skillset.

In practice, there are often gaps in the skillsets of small teams, who are expected to both be experts in these novel technologies and run an effective business. When technical skills are present, the “softer” skills (e.g., human resources) may not be. This means that there is a need for educational institutions and businesses themselves to grow capacity through on-the-job or course-based training. The following two quotes from entrepreneurs illustrate the issues with these skill gaps.

“Well, the biggest risk is the limited knowledge base that we have with the current team. So yes, we have an agronomist, yes, we have someone handling the production process, but these are people who've had on the job training and do not really have the technical expertise to be able to do that ... My colleague co-founder is a Biosystems engineer, so he works very well in developing the systems that we work with in the process for us but there's always things that are really beyond our scope of knowledge.”

(Sulati, Biotechnology).

“The e-mobility concept is still new to people in Kenya, and it's in East Africa and also in Africa. So mostly, this is used in European countries. So we don't have enough people here who have the right skill set. So having to find people so that you can create a team is not as smooth as it would be if it was something that existed before” (Matheka, Electric Mobility).

Respondents also reported that a **lack of awareness of customers** about the benefits of climate adaptation technologies was a challenge. Their products or solutions are new to the market and the potential customers seem to still be hesitant about adopting them, citing issues of safety and acceptance. This is illustrated in the following quote with regards to biogas and water recycling:

“The products that you're coming up with, sometimes people are a bit concerned. Just on the issue on the basis of; Is this thing safe? Can I use biogas that has been produced from poop? How safe is this water if I am eating vegetables that have been grown from recycled water? So, it is a big risk in terms of how people will accept these projects. Will people support these projects?” (Biko, Waste Management).

There is also the broader issue of behavioural change that comes with some of these products or services, and the general resistance to change in routine. Given this resistance due to a lack of information, some respondents reckon that building awareness will aid the entrepreneurs in capturing the larger market.

“I think one big challenge is that the products are very new. So, there's a lot of dedication required to convince people to buy the products. And also, people like to stick to their routine. So, getting a new product into that routine is not easy” (Ngina, Biotechnology).

“The market response, right now, everyone is trying to learn more of the electric vehicles as we agreed, it's something that is peaking. It's something new in the market and people are taking their time to learn. So, it's a wait and see scenario” (Kiio, Electric Mobility).

There was also a reported **lack of awareness amongst regulators** on the nuances of climate compatible business, leading to bureaucratic issues. Respondents interestingly discussed both over- and under-regulation: they are sometimes over-regulated in that they need to meet regulations in many different sectors (e.g., transport and energy in e-mobility), but under-regulated as there are no specific regulations that truly fit these emerging sectors such as in the production of honey. This could be addressed with increased political awareness of this market.

“So, one of the things is that our solutions are environmental, and issues to do with the environment are highly legislated. And you have to really factor in; make sure that your projects are able to protect environmental conditions. But sometimes these policies become a hindrance in terms of our development (in terms of our growth) because some

of the technologies that we're dealing with are new to some of the people that are supposed to be giving us okay" (Biko, Waste Management).

"So we are finding out very interesting things that are quite amazing, that need to be documented. So it's a disorganised field. Okay. It's not as well regulated as the others. Everybody and anybody is doing what they want to do, Which is not good for the industry. The standards are not there; So what exactly is honey? There is no definition of honey in this country. Because the standards we have are so basic, that any honey adulterated can pass, it's unfortunate. And that's why one of the best honey Labs is in Germany and they are able to test honey to the molecular level. They can tell you, this is honey from an acacia tree in Murang'a County, in Africa. That's very powerful!" (Mwendwa, Agriculture).

This issue seems to be further compounded by what the entrepreneurs perceive to be **unfriendly taxation and licensing policies**. Duty tax was particularly mentioned by those in the electric mobility sector as being particularly high in comparison to other East African countries. The number of permits and licences and the costs associated in processing or acquiring them were also considered to be very high and thus prohibitive in starting up a business. These issues apply more broadly to entrepreneurs across sectors, and not necessarily only climate adaptation entrepreneurs, particularly given Kenya's increasing taxes⁵⁵. This sentiment is illustrated in the following quotes:

"The other thing is licensing and taxation, Where the government has policies relating to licensing and taxation. For you to acquire licences and install our contractors. There are other documents that are very much needed. You have to submit the permits from the county, you have to submit a compliance certificate, you have to pay an application fee, you have to pay a client fee. You need to have a business, you need to have affidavits, you need to have a lease or title deed. When you compile all those costs, they are very high. It's a hindrance to turning knowledge into practice into business" (Gitonga, Renewable Energy).

"For every shilling you have, for every dollar you have, you would buy fewer units in Kenya, and more units in a country that has a lot of tax incentives. So that's a challenge. So for example, the viewer to buy a bus in Kenya for \$1. And buy that bus \$1 in China, two of them. So when you come to Kenya, you need to sink for another 70 cents, be able to pay duty on the bus. With Rwanda, you only need less than 10 cents, to be able to have that bus on the road in Rwanda. So when you look at that, that's a challenge also in itself. The government is doing a lot and there's a lot of promises and a lot of push and a lot of goodwill from the government just to be able to work around this and see how fast we can help incentivize this industry for adoption to be high" (Sahara, Electric Mobility).

"Developing laws that are friendly to the industry, and that will protect the industry, not

⁵⁵ <https://www.rfi.fr/en/africa/20240127-tax-hikes-meant-to-save-kenyan-economy-are-sending-businesses-broke>

hinder the industry. The challenge with some of the laws that are coming up of late is that they seem to like hammering the industry down, instead of protecting it and putting it up” (Mwendwa, Agriculture).

3.3.6 Growth Intentions and Needs

All the entrepreneurs had ambitions to grow beyond their current level of business. They mentioned various ways in which they intended to grow. The key ways they want to grow are summarised in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Key growth intentions emerging from the interviews.

Growth intention	Exemplary quote
Increased Production Capacity	<i>“I aim to grow my business by expanding the scale of production and also the market reach for my products. So, I intend to do this by increasing the acreage under cultivation. Currently, I’m doing one acre of vegetable farming and I’m also doing two acres of maize farming. I intend to increase this acreage to around three acres for vegetable farming and around five acres for maize farming and also introduce new crop varieties so that I can reach a wide consumer base” (Duma, Agriculture).</i>
Sales Growth	<i>“We’re about to grow our fleet by 5x and probably another 4x in the next year. So internally, we have the capacity to do that. But we are also building capacity locally so obviously with the big numbers of cars that we have with our hands, we will need to support them in terms of employing more people servicing the same class. Also doing partnership with companies to provide other support systems such as charging and parking and things like that” (Amani, Electric Mobility).</i>
Market expansion	<i>“We’re also looking at targeting a larger audience, we believe highly that we’ve not, we’ve not reached out to that rural smallholder farmer, we are targeting to reach as many as possible” (Dala, Agricultural Retail).</i>

Two of the most mentioned growth intentions were **increasing production capacity** (e.g., expanded farm sizes, fleet size) and **sales growth** (e.g., increased vehicle sales). Most of the entrepreneurs discussed their intention to pursue both as some of their business goals.

“I aim to grow my business by expanding the scale of production and also the market reach for my products. So, I intend to do this by increasing the acreage under cultivation. Currently, I’m doing one acre of vegetable farming and I’m also doing two acres of maize farming. I intend to increase this acreage to around three acres for vegetable farming and around five acres for maize farming and also introduce new crop varieties so that I can reach a wide consumer base” (Duma, Agriculture)

“We are always trying to grow our business. We’re always trying to grow our production capacity because I would say we have the best problem that a business could have which is being unable to satisfy completely the demand that we have in the market for our products, So, we’re always looking for avenues to grow, looking always being innovative around improving and increasing our production capacity, improving the efficiency of our processes” (Sulati, Biotechnology)

“We’re about to grow our fleet by 5x and probably another 4x in the next year. So internally, we have the capacity to do that. But we are also building capacity locally so obviously with the big numbers of cars that we have with our hands, we will need to support them in terms of employing more people servicing the same class. Also doing

partnership with companies to provide other support systems such as charging and parking and things like that” (Amani, Electric Mobility).

“So we are looking to do that to grow more buses. We raised our first year of operation, this is 2021. We imported two buses in 2022. And we wanted to be able to see whether we'll be able to grow the business from two buses, and imported an additional 15 buses in 2023. Our target for this year is to have 100 buses on the road by the end of the year so when you look at that, that is good. And we're talking about Kenya and Rwanda. That is what we are talking about” (Sahara, Electric Mobility).

One other growth intention that was mentioned was that of **market expansion**. The entrepreneurs wanted to reach out to more people and were planning to intentionally enter new markets. This has a possibility to create a dual benefit of increased income for entrepreneurs (as they gain new clients) and improved access for customers, as the entrepreneurs reach beyond low-hanging fruit towards harder to capture markets.

“We're also looking at targeting a larger audience, we believe highly that we've not, we've not reached out to that rural smallholder farmer, we are targeting to reach as many as possible. And then we are also looking at setting up a lot of branches Countrywide, because currently we just have our godown, which is in Kitengela. And then our main office, which is in Upper Hill, so we basically don't have many branches, Countrywide, so our operations are just within Nairobi” (Dala, Agricultural Retail).

“So we are looking to grow our business. Recently, we have just opened a new market in Rwanda. It's a few months old and doing well already with four buses on the road in Rwanda. So we want to grow our vision also around electric buses to be in almost in every major capital city in Africa. That's our desire. That's our vision. That's our dream. Starting with East Africa, East Africa, we have started in Rwanda and looking to do another, another few cities around East Africa very soon. So we want to grow our business. We want to be able to target those 60% of passengers that use public transport around Africa. We want to be able to tap into all those renewable energies“ (Sahara, Electric Mobility).

“Yes, we are trying to grow our business and our goals is to install more swapping stations around the country and later expand to East Africa and later to Africa” (Matheka, Electric Mobility).

“The restaurants are already there. We have some restaurants that are purchasing our honey, we are happy about that. We are also aiming at big hotels. And we are also getting into the food industry. But the food industry, we need a lot of it. So we have food manufacturing companies that need a bit of honey as sweeteners, so we are aiming at that. And then eventually we are also aiming at exporting the honey. So we are in touch with some consumers of honey out of this country. And so the moment we'll be able to hit the kind of targets we need to in terms of volumes, we'll be able to access those markets” (Mwendwa, Agriculture).

3.3.7 Perceived Opportunities

Entrepreneurs were also asked to identify key opportunities in the climate adaptation space. The key emerging themes are summarised in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Key opportunities emerging from the interviews.

Opportunity	Exemplary quote
Building synergies across value chains and supply chains	<i>"If people started working together instead of against each other. So that you can make sure the whole industry or the whole value chain can benefit. But then you work on the whole value chain together, and you don't work as separate individuals. So, if you look at the value chain of whatever it is, every key player, every company within that value chain should work together. Because I think if you work together, you can solve a lot of problems that are there" (Ngina, Biotechnology)</i>
Potential for circular economies	<i>"Creating circularity of waste. Something that we are trying to help in terms of, once we have these nutrients coming to our urban areas, apart from the energy that we've consumed out of the food which we consume quite less, maybe 25% of it, 75% can be recovered and taken back. So, these fertiliser businesses in the supply chain, those are opportunities that people can be able to get into." (Biko, Waste Management)</i>
Provision of charging infrastructure and gas stations	<i>"I think the first opportunity I'm seeing is charging infrastructure. So when you offer solutions around charging for electric buses, number one, there is a climate impact, at the same time you make money from what you're doing. It is like you're selling electricity to these buses. So that's an entrepreneurial opportunity, but at the same time, you're solving an environmental crisis." (Sahara, Electric Mobility)</i>
Sensitisation opportunities	<i>"There's an opportunity in terms of sensitization because they realise that one of the big challenges that we're facing is the awareness, you'll find that in urban areas like here, Nairobi, guys are really adapting, because they are aware of that. But if you want to target a larger group, like let's say, the entire country in Kenya, shouldn't there be that bit of sensitization where we are able to reach everyone, to spread this gospel on adoption of renewable energies, and also green transport?" (Emeka, Renewable Energy)</i>
Manufacture of organic cosmetics	<i>"We have petroleum wax and we have beeswax, okay, the more we consume petroleum products, the more we are actually emitting because it comes from petroleum, which has to be mined and stuff like that. And the processing of it comes with a lot of emissions. We need to also sensitise people to use these beeswax that don't come with any form of emission. That is a big opportunity. And anybody, everybody in beekeeping should get into this industry of manufacturing organic cosmetics." (Mwendwa, Agriculture)</i>
Opportunities in clean energy, e-mobility and water management	<i>"Another opportunity that I see is in the biodiesel, from waste. So there are people who are basically making this reusable energy from waste ... So if they're able to get the waste and be able to convert it into usable fuel, this will really help with emission of some of this harmful greenhouse gases that lead to climate change. So the biggest challenge that some of these people may face in the biodiesel sector ... is waste segregation, being able to separate the organic waste from the plastics and the glass. But, some people are coming up with more innovative ways of being able to do that." (Luna, Waste Management)</i>
Finance Opportunities	<i>"Maybe you can do leasing, for example, so someone doesn't need to come with Ksh 300,000 to own it, but he can come with Ksh 300 a day. He hires your product, for example, your bike, one uses it, and then returns it. So as an entrepreneur, you're greeted with some cash through leasing, and providing charging solutions." (Emeka, Renewable Energy)</i>

Entrepreneurs reported that there is room for businesses to build **synergies across value chains and supply chains**. One respondent suggested streamlining the supply chain and increasing efficiency by finding a route to market that 1) decreases the number of intermediaries 2) increases the profit margins of the farmer, 3) reduces agricultural losses in the supply chain and 4) reduces prices for the end-market.

"So, in terms of opportunities, there are great opportunities in the supply chain, improving the supply chain efficiency to reduce the impacts of climate change. So, one of it is, for example, on reduction of agricultural waste like farm waste. The majority of produce that is produced by our farmers, the majority of it, like 50%, ends up being wasted. So, if we can be able to improve the efficiency of the supply chain so that

whatever is produced goes to the market. It's a big opportunity for entrepreneurs to be able to fix it, because we eat food every day. If we can improve efficiency, reduce losses, we can improve the profitability of the farmers, reduce the prices of the limiting market and basically create sustainable job opportunities in the supply chain. So, I think in this economy, one area that we can focus on is how do we streamline our agricultural supply chain in a way that is sustainable because it is not sustainable if our farmers continue to farm at a loss. It is not sustainable, when 'Mama mboga' (grocery seller in the market) buys fresh produce, 50% of it gets spoiled. It is not sustainable when, just logistic handling because now ten People have to handle this food before it gets to the market, spoilage in the market is almost like a third of what came from the farm. Also, can we reorganise? There's an opportunity in reorganising the supply chain so that we can produce what consumers need and we transform that supply chain from a push model to a pull model, whereby the market is quite organised. We do what the market requires and therefore, give the information to the farmers in terms of how much to produce when" (Biko, Waste Management).

A different respondent shared about creating synergy in the climate adaptation **value chains** through cooperation instead of competition. They report how instead of having businesses constantly competing and trying to serve all functions in a particular value chain, co-benefits could be created if different businesses specialised in different value chain stages and cooperated. This is promising, as it speaks to room in the sector for increased, specialised players, and how this could benefit the whole system, as illustrated in the following quote:

"If people started working together instead of against each other. So that you can make sure the whole industry or the whole value chain can benefit. But then you work on the whole value chain together, and you don't work as separate individuals. So, if you look at the value chain of whatever it is, every key player, every company within that value chain should work together. Because I think if you work together, you can solve a lot of problems that are there" (Ngina, Biotechnology).

They also discussed the potential for **circular economies** to improve the effectiveness and profitability of waste management and agriculture while reducing input costs, as previously discussed in section 3.3.3.

"One is water, focusing on water treatment and water reuse. So water treatment means that water that will be wasted is reused. And also water that is not safe for human consumption can be treated, for example, using reverse osmosis and ultrafiltration. Then being used for consumption and agricultural purposes" (Kithika, Agriculture).

"Another space is basically the recycling, but couple it together with waste segregation. So people who come up with recycling, should think of recycling technology that solves also the issue of waste segregation. So that we can be able to separate some of these things: it will be a really game changer, to help with recycling of some of these products" (Luna, Renewable Energy).

"Creating circularity of waste. Something that we are trying to help in terms of, once we

have these nutrients coming to our urban areas, apart from the energy that we've consumed out of the food which we consume quite less, maybe 25% of it, 75% can be recovered and taken back. So, these fertiliser businesses in the supply chain, those are opportunities that people can be able to get into. Also, reusing the water to grow things like Napier for energy is another opportunity that people can adventure into" (Biko, Waste Management).

The entrepreneurs went further and shared **specific business opportunities** that other entrepreneurs can take advantage of if they desire to operate in the climate adaptation sector. The provision of **charging infrastructure** and gas stations was a business that was recommended by respondents in e-mobility, who currently see this as a roadblock towards increased uptake of electric vehicles. They had this to say:

"I think the first opportunity I'm seeing is charging infrastructure. So when you offer solutions around charging for electric buses, number one, there is a climate impact, at the same time you make money from what you're doing. It is like you're selling electricity to these buses. So that's an entrepreneurial opportunity, but at the same time, you're solving an environmental crisis" (Sahara, Electric Mobility).

"You realise that there are petrol stations outside here that most commonly will realise that fuel, fuel cars, but there's an alternative where you can have a gas station. So instead of having a fuel station, you have a gas station. Gas Station, the gas is so friendly to the environment, and is so cheap as compared to fuel. And if you look at the rate of wear and tear for the vehicles using the gas as compared to fuel there's a great improvement" (Emeka, Renewable Energy).

Another respondent highlighted the following **sensitization** opportunity within the climate adaptation space. This aligns with the challenge of lack of awareness and resulting friction towards behaviour challenge highlighted in the previous section.

"There's an opportunity in terms of sensitization because they realise that one of the big challenges that we're facing is the awareness, you'll find that in urban areas like here, Nairobi, guys are really adapting, because they are aware of that. But if you want to target a larger group, like let's say, the entire country in Kenya, shouldn't there be that bit of sensitization where we are able to reach everyone, to spread this gospel on adoption of renewable energies, and also green transport?" (Emeka, Renewable Energy).

A respondent in the bee-keeping business highlighted the manufacture of **organic cosmetics** as a business opportunity that currently exists:

"We have petroleum wax and we have beeswax, okay, the more we consume petroleum products, the more we are actually emitting because it comes from petroleum, which has to be mined and stuff like that. And the processing of it comes with a lot of emissions. We need to also sensitise people to use these beeswax that don't come with any form of emission. That is a big opportunity. And anybody, everybody in beekeeping should get into this industry of manufacturing organic cosmetics" (Mwendwa, Agriculture).

Several respondents further stated that there are opportunities in clean energy, mobility and water. These include biodiesel, clean cooking, and nutrition-based projects. Some of their responses are captured below:

“Another opportunity that I see is in the biodiesel, from waste. So there are people who are basically making this reusable energy from waste. And this basically helps solve the issue of some of these dumpsites that we usually find all over the place. So if they're able to get the waste and be able to convert it into usable fuel, this will really help with emission of some of this harmful greenhouse gases that lead to climate change. So the biggest challenge that some of these people may face in the biodiesel sector, and it's the biggest challenge that people living in the recycling sector have is waste segregation, being able to separate the organic waste from the plastics and the glass. But, some people are coming up with more innovative ways of being able to do that” (Luna, Waste Management).

“There are a lot of opportunities on the climate, well, on issues to deal with the environment, you know, especially in the areas of addressing clean cooking, because everyone must cook. So, clean cooking solutions will be the top, then food security, and sanitation” (Lule, Waste Management).

“The biggest opportunity for entrepreneurs right now in the climate space is Mobility. So, a huge contributor to emission of greenhouse gases is usually our mode of transportation. Yes, because most of our vehicles run on petrol and diesel. So the people who are right now investing in the electric mobility space might be able to really do well in that space. And also be able to minimise the emission of greenhouse gases. There are significantly more vehicles than the diesel generators that are used to power homes. So that's the biggest challenge and if they're able to basically enhance or to be able to solve that problem of moving, we can be able to get a pretty huge clientele, not purely just from people who are using their vehicles for personal use, but also people who are doing public transportation; not just buses, but you find some Ubers are using the gas and LPG. People in the mobility space really have an opportunity to really get into that case and do well” (Luna, Renewable Energy).

“If entrepreneurs provided water, then it would mean, as I had earlier said, it would enhance the chances of people adapting to climate change, building resilience and that has to come with issues to do with, say, planting vegetables and few other things that they can plant to enable them get vitamins to enable them get some good proteins and all that and also you see availability of water would go a long way in the long chain of for example if you have water you can keep some chicken, you can have some eggs, so all that is to build on resilience and then it will protect health. So, I believe there is an opportunity for entrepreneurs to provide water. So then to build on resilience, to protect health and save lives” (Juma, Water Management).

Finally, the respondents also mentioned that in the climate adaptation space there were unique opportunities in **financing**. The current challenge of accessing it has been stated to also be an

opportunity for both the entrepreneurs and the financial institutions:

“Also the products you're creating, for example, you realise that for someone to own our product they'll either take a loan, right? or maybe get financed somewhere, right? or even sell a property. But there are those people who don't have property, there are those people who can't access loans or finances to give them money. But as an entrepreneur, you can give an alternative solution where your business model actually might address this problem, maybe you can do leasing, for example, so someone doesn't need to come with Ksh 300,000 to own it, but he can come with Ksh 300 a day. He hires your product, for example, your bike, one uses it, and then returns it. So as an entrepreneur, you're greeted with some cash through leasing, and providing charging solutions. At the same time, you have created employment for someone who didn't have Ksh 300,000. But yeah, 300 shillings” (Emeka, Renewable Energy).

“Looking at the issue of financing electric buses. When you make the adoption of electric buses, easier, cheaper, cheaper, finance, greener finance is ideally thought to be cheaper. So that is an area where returns are high, returns are faster. If capital was extended there, the returns on the investment will be faster for financial institutions, ideally, compared to the combustion engine” (Sahara, Renewable Energy).

Other respondents posited that there was an entrepreneurial opportunity in selling carbon credits alongside their existing activities:

“The carbon markets are there, and entrepreneurs can approach that in so many ways that if they join organisations, that buy the carbon credits or form communities where their carbon credits can be bought. That would be an entrepreneurship opportunity. And it is, it could be available in so many ways. An example in our company, e-mobility solutions, you can sell those carbon credits. And so if you're planting trees, and you're organised in a group, you can also sell those carbon credits. So entrepreneurs can look at it in that way” (Matheka, Electric Mobility).

“Carbon crediting is a new thing among people in the rural areas and most people don't understand what carbon crediting is. When you think of people who are being told to plant trees, they don't understand the concept of carbon crediting. Especially having someone who has knowledge of carbon oxidation. You see like now, if you have someone who can be able to link between the factory and pay for the carbon credit. And the farmer who does the pricing of the products can have an opportunity where they can create a living for both the farmer and the companies that are reducing carbon emissions in the environment” (Asha, Agriculture).

3.3.8 Business Models Recommended

Entrepreneurs were asked about the most effective business models in this sector. The key factors that emerged are summarised in Table 8 below.

Table 8: Key Business Models emerging from the interviews.

Model	Exemplary quote
Customer-led Business Models	<i>"In coming up with this business model, first of all, you really have to understand the needs of the consumer. Because once you understand the needs of the consumer, then now you will develop a product or a solution or a value that addresses a problem. That will really simplify the process." (Biko, Waste Management).</i>
Partnerships and Collaboration centred models	<i>"Using collaborative partnerships and networks. Entrepreneurs can establish collaborations with NGOs, governments and other institutions to create networks for a more holistic and scalable approach" (Duma, Agriculture).</i>
Integrated Models	<i>"Integrated solutions provider. It involves combining seeds, technology and sustainable practice to provide comprehensive packages that will address diverse needs of farmers." (Duma, Agriculture)</i>
Pay as you go or Subscription model	<i>"So a subscription based model is what we're also going to have for some of these new products that we're developing, where somebody pays a certain amount per year, but the benefits are much more than the actual amount that they actually pay per year. So even with the solar installation systems that we're doing, we're also providing a cleaning service. So people could also pay a certain cost, and we would always be cleaning the solar panel. So there also needs to be some form of recurring revenue, not just a one-off cost. So I believe something like a subscription basis is pretty good." (Luna, Renewable Energy).</i>
Circular Model	<i>"I believe the best thing is to embrace a circular model where you are trying to make sure that nothing goes to waste, that everything has a use in the process or is able to be sold as a product so that you're able to close the loop and reduce your exposure as an entrepreneur" (Sulati, Biotechnology).</i>

Many of the entrepreneurs reported that **customer-led business models** are the most effective. This common theme, brought out without prompting, affirms much of the existing business literature. One respondent in the waste management sectors said:

"One of the biggest aims of a business model is that business models should be able to generate value and this value that has been generated has to have originated from the needs of the user. So, you cannot develop a business model unless you really understand the customer's needs. So, in coming up with this business model, first of all, you really have to understand the needs of the consumer. Because once you understand the needs of the consumer, then now you will develop a product or a solution or a value that addresses a problem. That will really simplify the process. When I've identified the need, then I'll be creative in terms of how do I deliver this? What channels do I use in terms of delivering the product? There are several channels, but now depending on the business and the consumer that you're dealing with, you will identify the most suitable channel for you to deliver" (Biko, Waste Management).

A respondent in the retail sector further articulates that having a customer-led business model ensures the long-term sustainability of a business:

"In the end, you need to solve a problem for a customer. That's the most sustainable kind of business. So, if you want to do something in climate adaptation, you need to think like, what can I do in this space to deal with climate adaptation, but solve a problem for a customer? That's the ultimate in business? Right? Yes, it is completely different. I think you get given money, and you solve a problem in a different way that has nothing to do with profit. But if you want to be entrepreneurial, and make money, then you have to solve a problem for the customer. And then you need to get close to the customer to understand what the problem is. What are the nuances, how can you build on it? Where can you do it better? How can you do it? et cetera" (Gathii, Food Retail).

Other respondents reported that **partnerships and collaborations** were a key component to their business models. Some of them mentioned that some of the most crucial partners needed in making their business models effective were financial institutions and suppliers.

“Partnerships with financial institutions for both the entrepreneur and the clients, the target client” (Lule, Waste Management).

“You can also as an entrepreneur, let's say you can partner with a manufacturer, and ask them to produce for you, let's say 2000 bikes, and then in turn, you go and you buy from them in wholesale, and then you go and sell them in pieces at your own at your own price that you've set. So it's also possible to become a dealer, maybe with the company or any other company that offered these products. You are going to become a dealer by the minute and they'll go and sell them at retail prices” (Emeka, Renewable Energy).

Other respondents stated that partnering with the government, who are usually the regulators, is a particularly important business model. They mentioned the opportunity for public-private partnerships, and to create more holistic interventions supported by both business and policy.

“I think the first one would be public private partnerships. When setting up, the infrastructure is capital intensive and expensive and you find that sometimes the government has idle facilities issues that haven't been used that are not in use or they have the infrastructure but they are unable to manage it or furnish it, so getting into a partnership with the government will give you an avenue where you have the infrastructure and you don't have to cater for a lot of the capital costs that are involved in setting up processing facilities” (Kithika, Renewable Energy)

“Using collaborative partnerships and networks. Entrepreneurs can establish collaborations with NGOs, governments and other institutions to create networks for a more holistic and scalable approach” (Duma, Agriculture).

This aligns with entrepreneurs' call for an **integrated approach** that will provide comprehensive packages to address diverse needs, and address the entrepreneurs motivation to address climate change and pursue profits too:

“Integrated solutions provider. It involves combining seeds, technology and sustainable practice to provide comprehensive packages that will address diverse needs of farmers” (Duma, Agriculture).

“Like I said, making sure that your business doesn't have to be either fully climate focused, or either fully money focused, but going with both as your means. And I think then, only when you find a fine balance there is where you can actually make an impact. So, I think you can never maybe right away 100% climate or 100% money, but you maybe start at 50/50. And then you grow the climate parts more and more and more” (Ngina, Biotechnology).

They also suggested a **pay-as-you-go or subscription model** to ensure consistent income

and to deal with the challenge of enhancing the affordability of their products.

“A subscription based model might actually be pretty good for some of these businesses. So a subscription based model is what we're also going to have for some of these new products that we're developing, where somebody pays a certain amount per year, but the benefits are much more than the actual amount that they actually pay per year. So even with the solar installation systems that we're doing, we're also providing a cleaning service. So people could also pay a certain cost, and we would always be cleaning the solar panel. So there also needs to be some form of recurring revenue, not just a one-off cost. So I believe something like a subscription basis is pretty good. For some of the people with these systems, if they're able to secure enough financing, they can come up with a payment system, where the person is just paying a certain amount to use the solar panels. So if we're able to secure enough grants or any form of financing, we can install solar panels on someone's roof and have them pay the same amount they would be deemed to give KPLC and after a certain period of time, they would own the solar system” (Luna, Renewable Energy).

“Talking from experience and from what I've seen in our company in the industry, the first business model that comes to mind is pay as you go. means somebody actually has already financed the asset but extends it to you at a much, much more lenient and easier terms. It's me buying a bus for 10 million shillings asking you for 1 million shillings. And for you to be able to pay me something every day, or every so often for me to be able to recover my 9 million shillings. So for me that's the big reason because it's an expensive solution. It's an expensive technology. It's an expensive business. So bearing that cost of financing and telling you to pay as you go as you make your money pay me as you run their technology pay me back. That is the best business model I see that revolves around sustainable solutions. I wouldn't be able to say I have another top of their mind but for me that will be the best business model for any person looking to do anything sustainable around” (Sahara, Electric Mobility).

Finally one respondent recommended a **circular model**, echoing previous discussions of circular economy opportunities.

“I believe the best thing is to embrace a circular model where you are trying to make sure that nothing goes to waste, that everything has a use in the process or is able to be sold as a product so that you're able to close the loop and reduce your exposure as an entrepreneur” (Sulati, Biotechnology).

3.4 Comparative Analysis with Community data

To understand whether the needs addressed by entrepreneurs align with needs on the ground, data from 1,023 household surveys conducted in Kenya in 2023 using the UPV approach were analysed. Particular focus was placed on climate change fears and adaptation strategies.

The survey data shows that community members are generally very worried about climate change. Respondents were asked how worried they are about climate change on a five point scale (i.e., not at all, slightly, moderately, very, extremely). 60% of respondents were very worried and 26% were extremely worried, for a total of 86% in the two highest categories. This indicates that climate change is a significant concern. It also aligns with the level at which climate change motivated surveyed entrepreneurs to start their businesses (i.e., 86% indicated that climate change was either an important or very important motivator to start their business).

When asked what extreme climate event they were most worried about, 76% of community respondents chose drought and 11% chose extreme heat. These heat related concerns are therefore much more worrying than flooding, which was selected as the greatest worry by only 5% of respondents. This aligns with the concerns addressed by agricultural businesses in our sample (e.g., improved farming to tackle drought-related food insecurity, improved beekeeping technology to manage extreme heat).

Community respondents were then asked to select the three most important items to them in the case of their most worrying climate event. These could be picked from a locally-tailored set of pictorial prompts. The top 10 most selected items are shown in Table 1. Borehole was the most frequently selected item (15%), followed by money (10%) and bible (7%). Based on these items, one can hypothesise respondents' intended adaptation strategies: seek alternative water sources, have finances to weather the event, and pray. These results align with entrepreneur responses in two ways. First, several entrepreneurs were looking to tackle issues of water security (i.e., through solar-powered irrigation). Second, entrepreneurs also recognised the need to provide ways to increase or diversify income to promote resilience in case of climate shock, and several shaped their businesses around this premise. As such, they are directly addressing the top two needs. With regards to the third need, it is unsurprising that entrepreneurs were not looking to in some way sell faith and prayer, which is already provided for by local religious institutions.

Table 1: Most prioritised items by respondents in the case of their most worrying climate event sorted in descending order. The count includes all first, second, and third selections.

Item	Count	% of all selections
Borehole	472	15%
Money	296	10%
Bible	218	7%
Clothes	207	7%
House	199	6%
Water	194	6%

Donkey and Cart	169	5%
Mobile Phone	142	5%
Irrigation	132	4%
Jerrycan	107	3%

In terms of climate change awareness, 57% of respondents reported the radio or TV as their main source of climate change information. This was followed by social events (18%) or word of mouth (15%). 11% of respondents indicated that they had received training or guidance related to climate change from the municipality, NGOs, community leaders, or other bodies. Thinking back to entrepreneur results, these results can help to inform awareness-raising strategies. Entrepreneurs cited a lack of awareness amongst the general population - it is possible they are simply targeting the wrong information sources to reach their target demographics.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

This working paper has presented evidence on entrepreneurial approaches to climate adaptation in Kenya. As entrepreneurship is critical in facilitating economically sustainable climate adaptation, it is important to establish best-practices to create thriving businesses in this sector. Evidence from previous studies indicates that these entrepreneurs remain poorly understood - this study aims to fill this information gap. A mixed methods study was undertaken to map the values and motivations of diverse climate adaptation entrepreneurs in Kenya to identify key opportunities and challenges that they perceive in this space as well as the best business models to create inclusive climate adaptation impact.

The diversity of adaptation measures was captured in the varying ways in which entrepreneurs articulated the adaptation needs that their businesses were meeting. We find that one of the main adaptation needs being met by entrepreneurs is the provision of resilient agricultural practices and inputs. This aligns with community data which found that drought and extreme heat were the climate events of greatest concern. The reduction of greenhouse gas emissions was another of the main needs that the entrepreneurs mentioned. Despite its categorization as a mitigation strategy in literature, it is perceived as adaptation to the entrepreneurs. These speak to the context-specificity of climate adaptation and the need for context-specific study.

The findings do echo extant literature on some of the challenges faced by entrepreneurs, such as financial and technical capacity gaps. However, the present study illustrates that despite the challenge in accessing appropriate finance, entrepreneurial opportunities in the climate adaptation space abound, particularly in clean energy, e-mobility and water management. The business model most recommended by the sampled entrepreneurs in the climate adaptation space in Kenya is a customer-led approach; their personal experience was of increased business resilience and competitiveness by using it. Partnership and collaboration centred

models and subscription business models were further recommended as a way to adapt to the challenge of accessing appropriate finance.

The lack of awareness amongst the consumer and the regulators created friction for the entrepreneurs in this study. A key policy recommendation of this study is therefore to focus on the sensitization of climate change to the population at large to enhance the adoption of climate adaptation solutions. Furthermore, regulatory authorities need to be sensitised and capacitated to support the entrepreneurs by creating conducive systems and structures within which to operate their businesses. This could take the form of sector-specific regulation in emerging sectors at the nexus of traditional policy portfolios (e.g., e-mobility at the nexus of transport and energy).

This study's limitation is that entrepreneurs from one region in Kenya were sampled. Entrepreneurs in other counties in Kenya may have other unique perspectives regarding challenges, opportunities and motivation based on their local contexts and their different lived experiences. However, this study does provide rich and nuanced insight into the unique perspectives of entrepreneurs in Kenya concerning climate adaption. Future research should expand the number of interviewees in various counties to develop a more representative sample. This study being the first step, it encourages the scope of future research to be wider to capture the variety of contexts and to gather more demographically disaggregated data so as to scale the inclusive impact.

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Appendix A: Full interview tool

Introduction

This project investigates inclusive and sustainable climate adaptation entrepreneurship in Kenya. It has three key aims. First, it aims to understand the motivations of entrepreneurs in the climate adaptation space with an intersectional lens. Second, it aims to identify their perceptions on the opportunities and challenges in the climate adaptation space in Kenya. And third, it aims to evaluate the business models they have adopted to support the development of innovative climate adaptation solutions.

We are conducting interviews with Kenyan entrepreneurs working in the climate adaptation space to understand their perceptions. The data from these interviews will be analyzed using a values framework to better understand entrepreneur motivations. The opportunities and challenges that entrepreneurs express will be compared with existing data on the key needs of local communities for climate adaptation. By capturing this information in a demographically disaggregated way, we aim to map pathways for inclusive environmental entrepreneurship to

serve diverse climate adaptation needs. We also aim to identify the business models which best drive innovation in the creation of climate adaptation solutions.

1. Do you consent to take part in the interview, and for the interview to be recorded?

About the business

2. Can you briefly describe your business?
3. What was your biggest motivation for starting this business?
4. What was the main impact you were aiming to create by starting the business?
5. What climate adaptation needs are you addressing in your business?
6. Who are your main customers?
Follow-up if not addressed in the response to the main question: Are there particular demographics you are serving or aim to serve?
7. Does your product or service significantly benefit historically disadvantaged groups?
If yes, which ones and how?
8. Are there any aspects of your business that you have had to change since it started?
If yes, could you explain why you have had to make those changes?

Business structure

9. Are you the sole owner of this business? If not, what is the ownership structure?
10. How are the prices for the products or services offered by your business set?
11. Are you trying to grow your business? If yes, what are your goals for growth, and what kind of support do you need to achieve those goals?
12. Does your business rely on any collaborators or partners to sustain its operation?
If yes, who and how?
13. What challenges or risks do you face in your ability to run and sustain your business?
14. When starting your business, did you receive any start-up funding or grants?
If yes, from who?
15. What kinds of funding has or does your business receive? For instance, does your business receive grants, loans, or other kinds of financing? If yes, from who?
16. What are the main inputs your business needs in order to provide its products or services? Where are they sourced from?
Follow-up questions if not answered by the main response:
 - a. *Are the inputs imported or are they produced within Kenya?*

- b. *Are the inputs bought from other businesses or are they free public resources?*

Business relationship to climate adaptation

17. Before your business started, did your customers attempt to meet their need for climate adaptation in other ways? If yes, how so, if you know?
18. Does your business solution build on, replace, and/or enhance your customers' previous attempts at climate adaptation? In each case, please describe how.
19. Does your business solution help people adapt to climate change in the short-term?
Prompt: For instance, does it help them to handle adverse climate effects that they're experiencing right now?
20. Does your business solution help people to adapt to climate change in the medium-term?
Prompt: For instance, does it help them to change their existing practices to cope in the medium-term?
21. Does your business solution help people to adapt to climate change in the long-term?
Prompt: For instance, does it facilitate long-term transformation of their usual practices?

Entrepreneur perceptions

22. What are the three key opportunities that you see for entrepreneurship to help with climate change adaptation? Please list them in order of importance.
*Interviewer to why-probe for each selection - responses will be coded against UPVs.
E.g., "You said that X is the most important opportunity. Why do you think X is a key opportunity?"*
23. What are the three key challenges that you see for entrepreneurs who want to start a business that addresses climate adaptation needs? Please list them in order of importance.
*Interviewer to why-probe for each selection - responses will be coded against UPVs.
E.g., "You said that X is the biggest challenge. Why do you think X is a key challenge?"*
24. What business models and approaches do you think are most effective for entrepreneurs in the climate adaptation space? Please list them in order of importance.
*Interviewer to why-probe for each selection - responses will be coded against UPVs.
E.g., "You said that X is the most effective business model. Why do you think X is the most effective?"*

Close

We would like to stay in touch with you in case we require any additional information, but also share updates on the outcomes of the study. It would be great to get insights and learn about what others are doing in the sector. We hope to develop a short practitioners report where we

will share the study outcomes. Is it okay if we call you to do this?

Appendix B: Final code list

The full codebook used in the survey coding is shown in the table below. The codes are sorted by group (alphabetically) and then by total uses in the collected data.

Group	Code	Total uses
Business Change	Business model	19
	Product Portfolio	10
	Marketing Strategy	5
	Type of Human Resource	1
CA	Replace	7
	Build on	6
CA Need	GHG Emissions	13
	Affordable clean energy	10
	Food Security	7
	Waste Management	6
	Resilient agricultural practices	5
	Affordable agricultural inputs	5
	Economic Opportunities	5
	Revitalise soil	3
	Health and Safety	2
	Re-forestation	2
	Water scarcity	1
	Noise Pollution	1
	Challenge	Finances
Limited Technical Expertise		9
Market Penetration		8
Licensing and Taxation		7
Access to resources		7
Perishable products		3
Competition		3
Demand exceeds Supply		3
Making the product affordable		3
Climate Variability		2
Consistency of supply due to climate change		2
Fluctuation in Foreign currency		2
Conflict/Security		1
Lack of specialisation in the market		1
Disruption in international logistics		1

Customers Previous attempt at CA	Yes	11
	No	5
E.Challenge	Cost of starting	17
	Hostile Business Environment	8
	Lack of Market awareness/knowledge	8
	Technical expertise	7
	Market Penetration	6
	Balancing Economic and Social Objectives in Business	5
	Demand-ability to pay	4
	Lack of Information	3
	Competition	3
	Measuring Impact	3
	User friendliness of solution	3
	Sustainability/Longevity	2
	Contextual relevance of products	1
	Self Doubt	1
	Dynamism in the CA Space	1
Effective Business Model	Prioritise Partnerships and Collaborations	7
	Customer Led Model	6
	Pay as you go	4
	Build, Operate, Transfer	3
	Diversify Business portfolio	2
	Technology forward	2
	Community Based models	2
	Social Enterprise	2
	Circular model	1
Financing	Grant	15
	Equity	9
	Family and Friends	1
	Debt/Loans	0
Growth Intention	Production Capacity	10
	Sales Growth	9
	Expand into new markets	7
	Increase Product Portfolio	5
	Efficiency of Processess	3
	Authorised Distributor	1
	Develop Partnerships	1
Growth Support	Funding	15
	Human Resource	7
	Market Sensitization	3

	Data	1
Impact	Provide Solution to Market	14
	Employment Opportunities	10
	Increased output in agriculture	6
	Decreased use of harmful chemicals	6
	Food Security	6
	Less emissions	6
	Avail Clean safe water	4
	Reduce post harvest loss	4
	More affordable and better quality solution	4
	Increase participation of youth in agriculture	3
	Sustainable farming practices	3
	Renewable energy	3
	De-forestation solution	3
	Save Water	2
	Improved Health	2
	Data driven decisions	1
	Waste Management	1
	Serving the rural areas	1
	Increased awareness of Climate Change	1
Inclusivity	Inclusivity	25
	Societal Minorities	21
	Gender	9
Main Customer	Organisations and Government	22
Main Customer	Individual Consumers	20
Main Inputs	Bought	1
Motivation	Solution to Problem	19
	Challenge in accessing solution	9
	Provide Affordable and Sustainable products	6
	Climate conditions	5
	Creating good income	4
	Innate interest	3
	Availability of technology	3
	Food Security	2
	Availability of information	1
	Green Energy Incentives	1
	Fair food distribution	1
Opportunity	Harness synergies in value chains	10
	Innovation in entrepreneurship	7
	Financing	5

	Circular economy-recycling	5
	E-mobility	5
	Renewable Energy	5
	Food Security	4
	Water Management	4
	Charging infrastructure	3
	Sanitation	3
	Increased employment opportunities	3
	Beeswax products	2
	Clean cooking solutions	2
	Climate changes	1
	Afforestation	1
Other	Customers Motivation	4
	Agility	1
	Decision Making	1
Partner/Collaborator	Suppliers	11
	Financial Institutions	8
	Business Customers	6
	Research Institutes	3
	Consultants	3
	Government	3
	Philanthropic Foundations	1
Product Pricing	Competitor based pricing	24
	Cost-based pricing	8
	Psychological pricing	3
Sources of Main Inputs	Local	17
	International	12
Start-up Funding/Grant	No	10
	Yes	6
Type of Business	Company	12
	Sole Proprietorship	4
	Partnership	1
Value	Innovation	139
	Entrepreneurship	113
	Preservation of the natural environment	109
	Accessibility to services	86
	Being informed	78
	Caring for others	72
	Income	70
	Understanding others	65

Continuous costs	60
Knowledge attainment (learning)	59
Collaboration	55
Acceptance by others	53
Community development	53
Access to finance	52
Wellbeing	44
Being understood	39
Access to area	37
Fixed costs	36
Practical skill attainment	32
Food security	31
Aspiration	25
Clean air	25
Connection	24
Duty (role fulfilling)	23
Water security	23
Support network	20
Availability of goods/products	19
Personal growth	19
Self-worth	16
Diversity	15
Morality	12
Altruism	11
Ownership	11
Togetherness (loved ones)	11
Trust	8
Travel (of people)	7
Hygiene & sanitation	6
Assets	4
Being healthy	4
Consensus	4
Equality	4
Freedom to move	4
Mental health	4
Security (from people)	4
Safety (from animals, items, nature)	3
Tradition	3
Transportation (of goods)	3
Freedom of choic	2

	Home (feeling)	2
	Privacy	2
	Respect from others	2
	Shelter	2
	Barter trade	1
	Faith	1
	Freedom of expression	1
	Recreation	1
	Medical treatment	0

Appendix C: Full survey tool

Climate Adaptation Entrepreneurship in Kenya: Survey

This project investigates inclusive and sustainable climate adaptation entrepreneurship in Kenya. It has three key aims. First, it aims to understand the motivations of entrepreneurs in the climate adaptation space with an intersectional lens. Second, it aims to identify their perceptions on the opportunities and challenges in the climate adaptation space in Kenya. And third, it aims to evaluate the business models they have adopted to support the development of innovative climate adaptation solutions.

We are conducting interviews and surveys with Kenyan entrepreneurs working in the climate adaptation space. The data will be analysed to understand motivations, opportunities, and challenges, as well as the business models that work best in climate adaptation. By capturing these data in a demographically disaggregated way, we aim to map pathways for inclusive environmental entrepreneurship to serve diverse climate adaptation needs.

This survey should take 5-10 minutes to complete. All the information that you share with us will only be used anonymously. We are collecting your name only to be able to associate survey data with interview data. Once this is complete, your name will be deleted. We will not share any identifying information that you provide. For more information, please refer to the participant information sheet provided by the research team.

Q1 Please enter your name. [Text]

Q2 Please select "yes" below to indicate that you wish to participate in the survey and consent to the usage of the information you provide in this research.

Yes (1)

Start of Block: About your business

Q3 What is the main sector your business falls under?

- o Agriculture (1)
- o Water and sanitation (2)
- o Energy (3)
- o Other - Please describe. (4) [Text]

Q4 What are your main products or services? Please list up to three.

- o First main product or service: (1) [Text]
- o Second main product or service: (2) [Text]
- o Third main product or service: (3) [Text]

Q4a If there are any other products or services you would like to highlight besides your main three, please list them here. [Text]

Q5 To what extent did climate change motivate your decision to start this business? Please rate the importance of this motivation on a scale from 0 to 4.

- o 0 - Not important at all (1)
- o 1 - Slightly important (2)
- o 2 - Moderately important (3)
- o 3 - Important (4)
- o 4 - Very important (5)

Start of Block: Payments

Q6 How do consumers pay for your products or services? Select all that apply.

- M-PESA (1)
- Cash (2)
- Other - Please describe. (3) [Text]

Q7 Are payments generally made on a one-off or on-going basis?

- o One-off (1)
- o Ongoing (2)

[If Q7 = One-off] Q7a How many customers does your business serve each day? [Number]

[If Q7 = Ongoing] Q7b How many active clients does your business have? [Number]

Q8 What is the price for each of your main products or services? Please provide the price in KSH and the unit. For instance, you could list “per item” as the unit if you are selling individual items, “hourly” if you are quoting for a service at an hourly rate, or “monthly” if you are quoting a monthly subscription fee.

	Price (KSh) (1)	Unit (e.g., per item, monthly, annually, etc) (1)
#{Q4/ChoiceTextEntryValue/1} (1)		
#{Q4/ChoiceTextEntryValue/2} (2)		
#{Q4/ChoiceTextEntryValue/3} (3)		

Q9 Broadly, what percentage of your customers or clients are female? Please estimate if you don't have an exact figure. [Number]

Start of Block: Employment

Q10 How many people are currently employed in your business? [Number]

Q11 Are all of your staff employed full-time?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

[If Q11 = No] Q11a How many of your staff members are employed part-time? Please enter the number. [Number]

Q12 How many of your staff members are female? Please enter the number. [Number]

Q13 How many management positions does your business have? Please enter the number. [Number]

Q14 Of those management positions, how many are filled by females? Please enter the number. [Number]

Q15 Could you provide an estimate for the average monthly wage of your employees?

- Up to 50,000 (1)
- 50,000-100,000 (2)
- 100,000-150,000 (3)
- 150,000-200,000 (4)
- Over 200,000 (5)
- Prefer not to say (6)

Q16 Could you provide an estimate of your own monthly wage from the business?

- Up to 50,000 (1)
- 50,000-100,000 (2)
- 100,000-150,000 (3)
- 150,000-200,000 (4)
- Over 200,000 (5)
- Prefer not to say (6)

Q17 How many jobs do you estimate has your business created directly in total since it started? [Number]

Start of Block: Growth and financing

Q18 How many shops or locations does your business have? [Number]

Q19 What was your business' revenue last month? Please estimate if you do not have an exact number. [Number]

Q20 Was last month's revenue less than, the same as, or more than usual?

- Less than usual (1)
- The same as usual (2)
- More than usual (3)

Q21 Are you trying to grow your business?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

[If Q21 = Yes] Q21a What are your goals for growth?

	% [Number 0-100]
Profit increase by ()	
Employment increase by ()	
Number of shops increase by ()	
Other: ()	

Q22 What types of funding has your business received in the past? Please select all that apply.

- Start-up funding (1)
- Donor funding (2)
- Concessional funding (3)
- Commercial financing (4)

[If Q22 = Start-up funding] Q22a Who provided your start-up funding, and what was the structure of the funding (e.g., grant, loan, etc.)? [Text]

[If Q22 = Donor funding] Q22b Who provided your donor funding, and what was the structure of the funding (e.g., grant, loan, etc.)? [Text]

[If Q22 = Concessional funding] Q22c Who provided your concessional funding, and what was the structure of the funding (e.g., grant, loan, etc.)? [Text]

[If Q22 = Commercial financing] Q22d Who provided your commercial finance, and what was the structure of the finance? [Text]

Start of Block: About you

We want to know about you so that we can understand how your business approach relates to your identity. Note that this data will only be used in anonymized aggregate in the research.

Q23 Please enter your age. [Number]

Q24 Please indicate your gender:

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Non-binary / third gender (3)
- Other (4) [Text]

Q25 Please indicate your marital status:

- Married (1)
- Divorced (2)
- Separated (3)
- Widowed (4)
- Never married (5)
- Other (6) [Text]

Q26 Please indicate whether you have a disability:

- Yes, I have a disability (1)
- No, I do not have a disability (2)

[If Q26 = Yes, I have a disability] Q26a What is the nature of your disability? [Text]

Q27 Please describe your ethnicity. [Text]

Q28 What is your home county? [Drop-down list of Kenyan counties]

Q29 Could you please indicate the composition of your household? Please indicate the count of each group in the table below, including yourself.

	Male (# of people)	Female (# of people)
Children (under 18 years) (1)		
Young adults (18-34 years) (2)		
Adults (35-69 years) (3)		
Elders (70 years or older) (4)		

Q30 Do you have any other occupation besides entrepreneurship?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

[If Q30 = Yes] Q30a Could you please describe the other occupation(s) you hold?

Q31 Could you please provide an estimate of your total monthly income including all your occupations?

- Up to 50,000 (1)
- 50,000-100,000 (2)
- 100,000-150,000 (3)
- 150,000-200,000 (4)
- Over 200,000 (5)
- Prefer not to say (6)

Q32 What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Primary (1)
- Secondary (2)
- Tertiary (3)
- Higher education (4)

- o Technical training (5)
- o No education (6)
- o Other - please describe: (7)

[If Q32 = Secondary, Tertiary, Higher education, Technical training, or Other] Q32a What type of secondary school did you attend?

- o Public (1)
- o Private (2)
- o Community school (3)
- o Other - please describe: (4)

Q33 What was the highest level of education that either of your parents completed?

- o Primary (1)
- o Secondary (2)
- o Tertiary (3)
- o Higher education (4)
- o Technical training (5)
- o No education (6)
- o Other - please describe: (7)

Appendix D: Full summary table of major findings

The following major themes were generated from the 22 interviews that were conducted. This integrates all findings from the tables presented in each subsection of the Results.

Dimensions	Themes	Exemplary Quote
Motivation of Entrepreneurs	Identification of gaps or issues	<i>"Being in the energy space, I saw a gap where commercial and industrial companies are able to afford and are able to incorporate renewable energy into their operations, yet there was a lack of solutions that are addressing rural communities ... So we saw that gap and thought we should be able to find a model where the rural communities can be able to increase their incomes and quality of life by having solutions that are powered by renewable energy"</i> (Kithika, Renewable Energy)
	Knowledge of existing solutions	<i>"Being in Africa, we also recognize that we are at the tail end of most of these discussions. Because if you see countries like the UK, Germany, Japan, China, they have already transitioned towards electric mobility. But normally for Africa we need to wait for something to be trained outside before it comes in."</i> (Amani, Electric Mobility)
	Desire to bring local solutions	<i>"We wanted to develop local technology, because when we came into the market we were like, okay, let's see, are there solutions in the market? And why are they not working? And one aspect that we found out was that the technology was quite expensive. So, technology's been on the market, but not affordable to people that should be able to take up these solutions."</i> (Biko, Waste Management)
	Desire to provide affordable solutions	<i>"The major problem was that farming fish is very expensive in Kenya due to the feed that is available. So, she started researching that and then based on that, she found out that</i>

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		<i>the feed is too expensive because of the protein components. So, she was like, instead of me joining the problem, let me try to fix the problem.” (Ngina, Biotechnology)</i>
	Ideals for a better life	<i>“My biggest motivation was to understand where food was coming from in order to make better decisions for the health of my family and I, and then that very quickly developed into the health of the planet as well, because of course, they’re so closely interconnected.” (Gathii, Food Retail)</i>
Perception of Business Impact	Reduction of pollution	<i>“The first impact we have made is on the environment, and no pollution, no noise pollution or air pollution, removing carbon from the atmosphere” (Sahara, Electric Mobility).</i>
	Water conservation	<i>“The more water is wasted in non-productive ways, the more we are affecting the climate .. the best way is about to look at how we can use the little water that we have because water as a resource, it’s never enough and guard it” (Juma, Water Management).</i>
	Forestation	<i>“Well, saving forests is the main impact. So, for us, we are providing a cooking solution or an energy solution that will stop people from cutting down trees” (Lule, Waste Management).</i>
	Affordable and quality products in the market	<i>“So, insects are a component of animal feed. So, it helps in replacement of soya and silver fish. So, it replaces other existing protein components of which we aim that insects are more stable in price and quality, which is often the problem in Kenya.” (Ngina, Biotechnology).</i>
	Increased agricultural output	<i>“We see amazing results with the fertiliser, like people double or triple their output for a year, as well as reduce the use of pesticides” (Ngina, Biotechnology).</i>
	Decreased (post-harvest) food and water wastage	<i>“So we provide cold storage and ice to fishers who then are able to go for longer fishing expeditions using the ice and then what this does is that it reduces post-harvest losses because you’re able to maintain the quality of the fish from when it is caught to the landing sites to the processing facility” (Kithika, Renewable Energy).</i>
	Increased income and resources	<i>“By providing better prices for the Fisher-folks, then increasing their climate resilience because there’s a lot more income they may be able to diversify to other economic activities and reduce their total reliance on just fishing as a source of income” (Kithika, Renewable Energy).</i>
	Inclusion of the youth and the low income earners in the labour force	<i>“The main impact that we are aiming to create in the long term is to have as many youths as possible getting into agriculture, more specifically into the agricultural value chain. So, the average age of the farmer currently is 57 years and over 75% of our population is below 35 years. So what happens when the current farmers disappear, so to speak? We’ll have a generation that does not know how to produce food” (Bahati, Agriculture).</i>
	Provision of the solutions to the underprivileged in society	<i>“And also probably another impact is ideally bridging the gap and also tapping all the untapped opportunities regarding to the rural holders because majority of the companies are working with people in urban areas, but we thought who is taking care of the rural farmers” (Dala, Agricultural Retail)</i>
Education of the customer on matters relating to climate change	<i>“Conversation that climate change is actually happening, and what can we do actively towards mitigating that and solutions that are working outside also the same the solutions that will work here, like if I take out your Prado and give you an electric vehicle, what sort of things would you benefit from?” (Amani, Electric Mobility).</i>	
Climate Adaptation Needs	Reducing greenhouse gas emissions	<i>“Air pollution is seen by the emission of combustion gases, greenhouse gases, just from the internal combustion that happens inside the engine. So, these electric buses ... they do not emit those gases into the atmosphere” (Sahara, Electric Mobility).</i>
	Provision of affordable and clean energy	<i>“We are really campaigning for renewable energies. I would say it’s campaigning on educating clients or potential clients on the advantages of adopting renewable energy technologies, especially the farmers who are using diesel generators. You know there are so many farmers who use diesel generators. These generators are polluting rivers. We try as much as possible to replace those diesel water pumps with solar water pumps” (Gitonga, Renewable Energy).</i>
	Provision of economic opportunities	<i>“Our bikes are easy bikes, they use battery, and this can be charged from either solar or electricity directly from the grid. So that means that we are promoting the use of energy, clean renewable energy and then at the same time solving the aspects of affordability</i>

		<i>really in the climate space, and that means our low-income earners can get extra money because our bike is cheaper to operate.” (Ekwee, Electric Mobility).</i>
	Resilience in agricultural businesses	<i>“Firstly, my business is employing efficient irrigation methods to counteract the impact of scarce rains. And secondly, my business is also utilising seeds specifically designed to thrive in dry conditions. These measures enhance the resilience of agricultural operations of my business. Ultimately, ensuring productivity even in the face of variable and challenging climate patterns.” (Duma, Agriculture).</i>
	Managing Waste	<i>“The biggest one there is reduction. Like now a lot of the organic waste is dumped. And there are already more and more movements on like, what can we do with the waste? So, I think for us we collect waste, and we make it into valuable products so that definitely reduces emissions” (Ngina, Biotechnology).</i>
Challenges Experienced	Access to appropriate finance	<i>“Currently there's a lot of financing for climate related products. Well, that financing is not available to low-income individuals. Like the financing itself is for SMEs and above. The youths and the women who are disadvantaged, unless they are in those government initiatives for disability, they won't get the financing. Because the financing is based on the company, the financial documents that you have. You need to submit bank statements. The financing to low-income earners is very hard” (Gitonga, Renewable Energy).</i>
	Lack of technical capacity	<i>“Well, the biggest risk is the limited knowledge base that we have with the current team. So yes, we have an agronomist, yes, we have someone handling the production process, but these are people who've had on the job training and do not really have the technical expertise to be able to do that [...]. My colleague co- founder is a Biosystems engineer [...] but there's always things that are really beyond our scope of knowledge.” (Sulati, Biotechnology).</i>
	Lack of consumer and regulator awareness	<i>“The products that you're coming up with, sometimes people are a bit concerned. Just on the issue on basis of; Is this thing safe? Can I use biogas that has been produced from poop? How safe is this water if I am eating vegetables that have been grown from recycled water? So, it is a big risk in terms of how people will accept these projects. Will people support these projects?” (Biko, Waste Management).</i>
	Unfriendly taxation and licensing policies	<i>“The other thing is licensing and taxation, Where the government has policies relating to licensing and taxation. For you to acquire licences and install our contractors. There are other documents that are very much needed. You have to submit the permits from the county, you have to submit a compliance certificate, you have to pay an application fee, you have to pay a client fee. You need to have a business, you need to have affidavits, you need to have a lease or title deed. When you compile all those costs, they are very high. It's a hindrance to turning knowledge into practice into business.” (Gitonga, Renewable Energy).</i>
Growth Intentions	Increased Production Capacity	<i>“I aim to grow my business by expanding the scale of production and also the market reach for my products. So, I intend to do this by increasing the acreage under cultivation. Currently, I'm doing one acre of vegetable farming and I'm also doing two acres of maize farming. I intend to increase this acreage to around three acres for vegetable farming and around five acres for maize farming and also introduce new crop varieties so that I can reach a wide consumer base” (Duma, Agriculture).</i>
	Sales Growth	<i>“We're about to grow our fleet by 5x and probably another 4x in the next year. So internally, we have the capacity to do that. But we are also building capacity locally so obviously with the big numbers of cars that we have with our hands, we will need to support them in terms of employing more people servicing the same class. Also doing partnership with companies to provide other support systems such as charging and parking and things like that” (Amani, Electric Mobility).</i>
	Market expansion	<i>“We're also looking at targeting a larger audience, we believe highly that we've not, we've not reached out to that rural smallholder farmer, we are targeting to reach as many as possible” (Dala, Agricultural Retail).</i>
Perceived Opportunities	Building synergies across value chains and supply chains	<i>“If people started working together instead of against each other. So that you can make sure the whole industry or the whole value chain can benefit. But then you work on the whole value chain together, and you don't work as separate individuals. So, if you look at the value chain of whatever it is, every key player, every company within that value chain should work together. Because I think if you work together, you can solve a lot of problems that are there” (Ngina, Biotechnology)</i>

	Potential for circular economies	<i>"Creating circularity of waste. Something that we are trying to help in terms of, once we have these nutrients coming to our urban areas, apart from the energy that we've consumed out of the food which we consume quite less, maybe 25% of it, 75% can be recovered and taken back. So, these fertiliser businesses in the supply chain, those are opportunities that people can be able to get into." (Biko, Waste Management).</i>
	Provision of charging infrastructure and gas stations	<i>"I think the first opportunity I'm seeing is charging infrastructure. So when you offer solutions around charging for electric buses, number one, there is a climate impact, at the same time you make money from what you're doing. It is like you're selling electricity to these buses. So that's an entrepreneurial opportunity, but at the same time, you're solving an environmental crisis." (Sahara, Electric Mobility).</i>
	Sensitisation opportunities	<i>"There's an opportunity in terms of sensitization because they realise that one of the big challenges that we're facing is the awareness, you'll find that in urban areas like here, Nairobi, guys are really adapting, because they are aware of that. But if you want to target a larger group, like let's say, the entire country in Kenya, shouldn't there be that bit of sensitization where we are able to reach everyone, to spread this gospel on adoption of renewable energies, and also green transport?" (Emeka, Renewable Energy).</i>
	Manufacture of organic cosmetics	<i>"We have petroleum wax and we have beeswax, okay, the more we consume petroleum products, the more we are actually emitting because it comes from petroleum, which has to be mined and stuff like that. And the processing of it comes with a lot of emissions. We need to also sensitise people to use these beeswax that don't come with any form of emission. That is a big opportunity. And anybody, everybody in beekeeping should get into this industry of manufacturing organic cosmetics." (Mwendwa, Agriculture).</i>
	Opportunities in clean energy, e-mobility and water management	<i>"If people started working together instead of against each other. So that you can make sure the whole industry or the whole value chain can benefit. But then you work on the whole value chain together, and you don't work as separate individuals. So, if you look at the value chain of whatever it is, every key player, every company within that value chain should work together. Because I think if you work together, you can solve a lot of problems that are there" (Ngina, Biotechnology)</i>
	Finance Opportunities	<i>"Creating circularity of waste. Something that we are trying to help in terms of, once we have these nutrients coming to our urban areas, apart from the energy that we've consumed out of the food which we consume quite less, maybe 25% of it, 75% can be recovered and taken back. So, these fertiliser businesses in the supply chain, those are opportunities that people can be able to get into." (Biko, Waste Management).</i>
Business Models Recommended	Customer-led Business Models	<i>"In coming up with this business model, first of all, you really have to understand the needs of the consumer. Because once you understand the needs of the consumer, then now you will develop a product or a solution or a value that addresses a problem. That will really simplify the process" (Biko, Waste Management)</i>
	Partnerships and Collaboration centred models	<i>"Using collaborative partnerships and networks. Entrepreneurs can establish collaborations with NGOs, governments and other institutions to create networks for a more holistic and scalable approach" (Duma, Agriculture).</i>
	Integrated Models	<i>"Integrated solutions provider. It involves combining seeds, technology and sustainable practice to provide comprehensive packages that will address diverse needs of farmers" (Duma, Agriculture)</i>
	Pay as you go or Subscription model	<i>"So a subscription based model is what we're also going to have for some of these new products that we're developing, where somebody pays a certain amount per year, but the benefits are much more than the actual amount that they actually pay per year. So even with the solar installation systems that we're doing, we're also providing a cleaning service. So people could also pay a certain cost, and we would always be cleaning the solar panel. So there also needs to be some form of recurring revenue, not just a one-off cost. So I believe something like a subscription basis is pretty good." (Luna, Renewable Energy).</i>
	Circular Model	<i>"I believe the best thing is to embrace a circular model where you are trying to make sure that nothing goes to waste, that everything has a use in the process or is able to be sold as a product so that you're able to close the loop and reduce your exposure as an entrepreneur." (Sulati, Biotechnology).</i>